

19ENV09 (MetroPEMS) Improved vehicle exhaust quantification by portable emission measurement systems metrology

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1 Introduction

This document describes the main findings extracted from the work related the MetroPEMS project. The activities were performed according to the Joint Research Project protocol of the “Improved vehicle exhaust quantification by portable emission measurement systems metrology” (MetroPEMS) project. One of the key objectives of the MetroPEMS project was to develop application-oriented calibration procedures and uncertainty budgets for Portable Emission Measurement Systems (PEMS) in dynamic, real-world conditions. PEMS- devices are on-board emission measurement systems used in vehicle type-approval for measuring vehicle real driving emissions (RDE) on road in real-world conditions. Commercial PEMS devices used for type approval are typically smaller devices compared to the equipment used in laboratory conditions. The PEMS-devices intended for light passenger car measurements consists of a gas-PEMS unit, particle number (PN) counter and an exhaust mass flow meter (EFM). The content described in this report consists of an entity of activities conducted for evaluating the performance of current state-of-the-art commercial PEMS devices and beyond. The main motivation for this work was to validate and to define factors affecting the performance of PEMS devices. Another key motivation was to study the correlation for PEMS response between laboratory and RDE measurements. This evaluation was performed both on a system level and for the individual PEMS channels, CO₂, CO, NO, NO₂, PN, exhaust mass flow.

1.1 An overview of PEMS testing and the RDE-regulation

The type approval of motor vehicles with respect to emissions from light passenger and commercial vehicles (Euro 5 and Euro 6) sold in the EU follow the Regulation (EC) No 715/2007 set by the European Commission (EC) [1]. This regulation establishes the general technical requirements of motor vehicles, such as required emission limits measured in controlled laboratory conditions. During the deployment of the current emission class, Euro 6, the type approval process has been supplemented and updated with regulations, which covers vehicle emission measurements in real world conditions using Portable Emission Measurement Systems (PEMS). A specific RDE test procedure was initially developed and deployed in the EU and is defined in Annex IIIA of Regulation 692/2008 [2]. Since then, the Regulation 692/2008 has been repealed by an updated version, commission regulation (EU) 2017/1151 [3] with its further supplements amended in 2018, known as commission regulation (EU) 2018/1832 [4]. RDE-testing has been mandatory in the type-approval process for light passenger and commercial vehicles sold in the EU region since 2016. Since then, the RDE test procedure has been amended and supplemented with four RDE packages (RDE1 – RDE4) and announced in 2022, updates for Euro 6e. The different RDE packages include updates related to permissible PEMS tolerances and uncertainties, also known as conformity factors (CF) and widening of boundary limits among others. RDE4 is currently in force but will eventually be replaced by the newest revision, Euro 6e regulation. Euro 6e, was adopted in August 2022, which will take effect between September 2023 and September 2024 depending on vehicle type. The current RDE-procedure legislation follows procedure described in the commission regulation (EU) 2017/1151 including its revisions or by the latest amendment, Commission regulation (EU) 2023/443 [5] includes updates for cars type-

approved as Euro 6e vehicles. For Euro 6e, the permissible analyser drifts over a PEMS tests and redefines deviations for laboratory validations were revised, among others. The RDE tests are executed in parallel with regular in-laboratory tests following the WLTP test procedures described in the UNECE Global technical regulation (GTR) [6]. In order to fulfil the required accuracy of the on-road measurements, the regulation determines the permissible tolerance of the used PEMS equipment. Because PEMS equipment are known to typically have a higher uncertainty compared to laboratory tests, the EU commission introduced a method to take this into account, so called not-to-exceed (NTE) concept. The NTE represents separate type approval limits that consists of the sum of laboratory limits and a measurement safety margin named conformity factor (CF). The CF factor was initially utilized only for NO_x and PN emissions, as shown in Table 1-1. The required quality standards of the PEMS-equipment in terms of linearity is shown in

Table 1-2.

The regulation also defines requirements for PEMS the minimum device configuration and specifications for the installation. For the EFM, flow tube diameter must not be smaller than exhaust pipe, but EFM cross section may be smaller than total outlet diameter. Additionally, EFM flow range should be selected based on the expected maximum flow range, and the exhaust flow range should cover at least 75 % of EFM full range [3]. The required accuracy for the EFM device is set in the RDE-regulation following: the deviation of the EFM reading from the reference flow value, shall not exceed +/-3% of the reading, 0.5% of full scale or +/-1.0 % of the maximum flow at which the EFM has been calibrated, whichever is larger. [3] The vehicle speed should be acquired from a GPS -signal, ambient conditions are collected using a pressure- and humidity sensor connected to the PEMS-unit. Vehicle data, such as load, temperatures, engine and vehicle speed are followed through connecting the PEMS unit to vehicle OBD.

Table 1-1 Conformity factors of PEMS testing by RDE-package

RDE procedure	Effective year	NO _x CF	PN CF
2nd RDE package	2017 – 2019	2.1	1.5
3rd RDE package	2020 - 2021	1.5	
4th RDE package	2021 – 2023	1.43	
Euro 6e	2023 –	1.1	1.34

Table 1-2 The linearity requirements of PEMS-equipment in 2017/1151

Linearity requirements of measurement parameters and systems [3]

Measurement parameter/instrument	$X_{min} \times (a1 - 1) + a0$	Slope a1	Standard error SEE	Coefficient of determination r2
Fuel flow rate	≤ 1 % max	0.98–1.02	≤ 2 %	≥ 0,990
Air flow rate	≤ 1 % max	0.98–1.03	≤ 2 %	≥ 0,990
Exhaust mass flow rate	≤ 2 % max	0.97-1.03	≤ 3 %*	≥ 0,990
Gas analysers	≤ 0,5 % max	0.99-1.01	≤ 1 %	≥ 0,998
PN analysers	≤ 5 % max	0.85-1.15	≤ 10 %	≥ 0,950

*(increased from 2 % to 3% in EC regulation 2018/1832)

Prior to any RDE-testing, the vehicle and PEMS configuration must be validated in laboratory conditions. The validation process is executed by comparing the response of the PEMS device with laboratory grade emission measurement equipment on a chassis dynamometer. During the process, the PEMS must be installed on the vehicle dedicated for the RDE test. The permissible tolerances of this validation are given in the RDE 4 regulation (2017/1151) according to Table 1-3. For example, for NO_x, the limits in the RDE4 regulation are set to ± 15% of the result or 15 mg/km, whichever is larger.

Table 1-3 Permissible tolerances for PEMS-results in laboratory validation against CVS

Permissible tolerances for PEMS validation in laboratory conditions CVS	
Parameter [Unit]	Permissible tolerances
Distance [km]	± 250 m of the laboratory reference
THC [mg/km]	± 15 mg/km or 15 % of the laboratory reference, whichever is larger
CH ₄	± 15 mg/km or 15 % of the laboratory reference, whichever is larger
NMHC [mg/km]	± 20 mg/km or 20 % of the laboratory reference, whichever is larger
PN [# /km]	1*10 ¹¹ from particulate/km or 50% of reference acquired in laboratory, whichever is larger*
CO [mg/km]	± 150 mg/km or 15 % of the laboratory reference, whichever is larger**
CO ₂ [g/km]	± 10 g/km or 10 % of the laboratory reference, whichever is larger
NO _x [mg/km]	± 15 mg/km or 15 % of the laboratory reference, whichever is larger***
* the permissible tolerance for NO _x has been reduced in Euro 6e to 8*10 ¹¹ #/km or 42 % of the laboratory reference, whichever is larger ** the permissible tolerance for NO _x has been reduced in Euro 6e to ± 100 mg/km or 15 % of the laboratory reference, whichever is larger *** the permissible tolerance for NO _x has been reduced in Euro 6e to ± 10 mg/km or 12.5 % of the laboratory reference, whichever is larger	

The PEMS device requires a calibration check prior and after a valid RDE test. The calibration gas qualities should meet the requirements of the RDE regulation. The pre- and post tests are advised to take place as close to the actual RDE measurement as possible. In order to minimize the analyser drift, the zero and span calibration should be conducted at conditions that resembles the temperature of the equipment during the RDE test. The calibration procedure allows a zero and span adjustment of the gas analyser in the pre- test. After the RDE-test is complete, a post test is performed to determine the analyser zero and span drifts. The drifts are calculated based on the difference in calibration response between the pre and post- tests. The RDE-regulation defines the permissible drift for both zero and span values. The permissible analyser drift over a PEMS test is defined in table 3.

Table 1-4 Permissible analyser drift over a PEMS test

Permissible analyser drift over a PEMS test

<i>Pollutant</i>	<i>Zero response drift</i>	<i>Span response drift</i>
CO ₂	≤ 2000 ppm per test	≤ 2 % reading or 2000 ppm per test, whichever is larger
CO	≤ 75 ppm per test	≤ 2 % reading or 75ppm per test, whichever is larger
NO ₂	≤ 5 ppm per test	≤ 2 % reading or 5 ppm per test, whichever is larger
NO/NO _x	≤ 5 ppm per test*	≤ 2 % reading or 5 ppm per test, whichever is larger*
CH ₄	≤ 10 ppmC per test	≤ 2 % reading or 10 ppmC per test, whichever is larger
THC	≤ 10 ppmC per test	≤ 2 % reading or 10 ppmC per test, whichever is larger

*Euro 6e reduces the permissible NO_x drift for zero and span to 3 ppm per test. Further PN shall not drift more than 5000 #/cm³ per test.

The calibration gases for the PEMS equipment are chosen to match the range of pollutant concentrations expected during the RDE test following:

- Should cover at least 90 % of the concentration values obtained from 99% of the measurements of the valid parts of the emission test.
- For CO₂, range of 10 - 14 % is recommended
- For NO_x, 1500 - 2000 ppm is recommended

For PN, zero level is checked by sampling ambient air using a HEPA-filter for at least of 2 min. The zero level for PN shall not exceed the permitted values defined in the RDE-regulation. The EFM shall be purged and prepared for the measurements in accordance to the device manufacturer.

All measured data are collected through the PEMS-system and calculated by moving averaging windows (MAW) method. This method divides the test into sub sections (windows) and uses the distance specific average CO₂ emissions of each window to assess the normality of operating conditions. However, because the MAW method is solely intended for defining the vehicle emission in regulatory purposes, the process was excluded from the work described in this report.

2 Methodology

2.1 The approach for performance evaluation of PEMS devices

The performance evaluation of the PEMS devices were performed by setting up a test matrix consisting of both in laboratory tests and RDE measurements. The PEMS devices were evaluated between 2021 and 2023 using real world applications, i.e. with four Euro 6 emission class passenger cars. The tests were executed in two countries, Finland and Denmark. During the work four PEMS devices were evaluated, three commercially available PEMS devices and the project PEMS device, known as the goldenPEMS. The PEMS devices evaluated may be divided by device technology into two device types as described in Table 2-1. One commercial PEMS device was remain stationary in each country for the whole test period (one type 1 PEMS in both countries), meanwhile two of the PEMS devices (type 2 PEMS devices), one commercial PEMS and the goldenPEMS were sent between the two countries for back-to-back testing with the type 1 PEMS devices, whenever applicable. The performance evaluation started in Finland, where the two different PEMS types were installed in series. This process was repeated for two vehicles in each country. Then a series of CVS validations in laboratory conditions were conducted using the WLTC cycle, followed by a series of RDE tests. After the evaluation was completed in Finland, the type 2 PEMS device was sent to Denmark for further testing evaluation. There, type 1 and type 2 PEMS devices were similarly tested with two other vehicles in RDE conditions. This process was repeated for both the commercial type 2 PEMS device and the goldenPEMS as show in Figure 2-1.

The test campaigns were timed such that device robustness of PEMS type 1 could be studied and any deterioration effects of e.g. device ageing or other factors could be assessed. Therefore, all tests conducted with the commercial devices type 1 were scheduled such that the device would be either as close to its annual service interval, or tested just after the annual service, as shown in Figure 2-1. Because the objective of the work described in this deliverable was to study factors related to PEMS devices and technologies rather than factors influencing post processing, the PEMS results were not calculated as MAW results as described in chapter 1.1 *An overview of PEMS testing and the RDE-regulation* but were instead analysed based on momentary and cumulative data produced by the PEMS devices. The data was therefore addressed solely either as signals consisting of exhaust concentration received from individual PEMS channels or as exhaust mass (momentary, average and cumulative mass) calculated from the exhaust concentration and EFM mass flow.

Table 2-1 A description of the two PEMS types tested

<i>Component</i>	<i>PEMS type 1</i>	<i>PEMS type 2</i>
<i>CO₂</i>	<i>ND-IR</i>	<i>ND-IR</i>
<i>CO</i>	<i>ND-IR</i>	<i>ND-IR</i>
<i>NO</i>	<i>ND-UV</i>	<i>CLD</i>
<i>NO₂</i>	<i>ND-UV</i>	<i>PAS</i>
<i>PN</i>	<i>ADC</i>	<i>CPC</i>
<i>EFM</i>	<i>Pitot</i>	<i>Pitot</i>

Figure 2-1 An overview of the test principle conducted between 2021 - 2023

Make	Model	MY	Emission class	Fuel type	Drivetrain type
Skoda	Octavia	2017	Euro 6 d-TEMP	Gasoline	Manual
Skoda	Octavia	2019	Euro 6 d-TEMP	Diesel	Automatic
Toyota	C-HR	2016	Euro 6	Gasoline	Hybrid + Automatic
Peugeot	308	2020	Euro 6	Diesel	Manual

Figure 2-2 Skoda Octavia diesel

Figure 2-3 Skoda Octavia gasoline with two PEMS systems installed.

Figure 2-4 Toyota C-HR gasoline hybrid with two PEMS systems installed.

Figure 2-5 Peugeot 308 diesel with two PEMS systems installed.

3 Results performed with the commercial PEMS devices

3.1 Pre- and post- test response

The zero and span response in the pre and post tests of one type 1 PEMS device was systematically followed over a three year period (years 2021 – 2023). The pre/post response data was analyzed for studying the deterioration effects throughout the usage of the device. This allowed to quantify the typical device response over time, simultaneously accounting for any trend changes caused by usage or device age.

Table 3-1 Describes the span concentrations used in the campaign per time frame. The span concentrations were initially chosen based on initial knowledge of the Euro 6 emissions. However, the concentrations were later adjusted to more efficiently match the gas matrix of given vehicles.

Table 3-1 Span concentrations used during the test campaign.

	Year	2021	2022	2023
Span standard	Concentration			
CO₂	[%]	15	16	16
CO	ppm	40200	9950	9950
NO	ppm	3060	1255	1255
NO₂	ppm	1500	1500	625

Table 3-2 shows the pre/post test response for the ND-IR based devices accounting for CO₂ and CO compared to the permissible tolerances defined in the RDE regulation. Corresponding results for the ND-UV based NO and NO₂ results are shown in Table 3-3 and for the ADC based PN analyser in Table 3-4. Any cells marked in green pass the requirements defined in any regulation, meanwhile cells marked with red exceeds RDE 4 regulation, and cells marked with yellow exceeds the updated, Euro 6e requirements.

The acquired zero and span drift data indicate that the ND-IR device accounting for CO₂ performed well within the requirements of current regulation. The absolute span drift for CO₂ remain within ± 0.5 % in all 28 tests regardless of the PEMS status, aged or serviced. Furthermore, the zero drift was concluded as 0 for 27 of the tests. No systematic trends were found for neither zero nor span drifts as shown in Figure 3-1.

Correspondingly, the performance of the ND-IR CO analyzer was concluded with two exceptions satisfactory. Before the service period for both 2021 and 2022, the PEMS ND-IR for CO showed signs of device issues or malfunctions, resulting in zero drifts exceeding the permissible tolerances. After consulting with the PEMS manufacturer, the ND-IR device was serviced in advance, which restored the performance of the ND-IR unit. Beyond these failures, the pre/post drift performance of the CO ND-IR was found robust, with a span drift typically of ± 0.5 %, and zero typically below 50 % of the permissible zero drift limit. No systematic trends were found for neither zero nor span drifts as shown in Figure 3-1.

Table 3-2 CO₂ and CO pre/post response for PEMS type 1 ND-IR between years 2021 to 2023

Test #	Timeline	Test type	CO ₂ ND-IR							CO ND-IR							
			span standard	Permissible zero drift	zero drift	Permissible span drift	span drift	Permissible span drift	span drift	span standard	Permissible zero drift	zero drift	Permissible span drift	span drift	Permissible span drift	span drift	
			[%]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[%]	[%]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[%]	[%]	
1	Before service 2021	WLTC	15	1000	0	3000	-300	2%	-0.2%	40200	50	155	804	783	2%	1.9%	
2		RDE	15	2000	0	3000	-200	2%	-0.1%	40200	75	7	804	21	2%	0.1%	
3		WLTC	15	1000	0	3000	100	2%	0.1%	40200	50	1	804	-17	2%	0.0%	
4		RDE	15	2000	0	3000	-100	2%	-0.1%	40200	75	-16	804	-161	2%	-0.4%	
5		RDE	15	2000	0	3000	-400	2%	-0.3%	40200	75	-1	804	-74	2%	-0.2%	
6		RDE	15	2000	0	3000	0	2%	0.0%	40200	75	8	804	-4	2%	0.0%	
7	After service 2021	WLTC	15	1000	0	3000	-200	2%	-0.1%	40200	50	2	804	-5	2%	0.0%	
8		WLTC	15	1000	0	3000	0	2%	0.0%	40200	50	3	804	-47	2%	-0.1%	
9		WLTC	15	1000	0	3000	-100	2%	-0.1%	40200	50	-21	804	-42	2%	-0.1%	
10	Before service 2022	WLTC	16	1000	0	3200	-600	2%	-0.4%	9950	50	-3	199	-53	2%	-0.5%	
11		WLTC	16	1000	0	3200	-700	2%	-0.4%	9950	50	18	199	19	2%	0.2%	
12		WLTC	16	1000	0	3200	-100	2%	-0.1%	9950	50	0	199	-17	2%	-0.2%	
13		RDE	16	2000	0	3200	100	2%	0.1%	9950	75	21	199	47	2%	0.5%	
14		WLTC	16	1000	0	3200	-600	2%	-0.4%	9950	50	24	199	29	2%	0.3%	
15		WLTC	16	1000	0	3200	-100	2%	-0.1%	9950	50	1	199	-35	2%	-0.4%	
16		RDE	16	2000	0	3200	-800	2%	-0.5%	9950	75	5	199	-32	2%	-0.3%	
17		RDE	16	2000	0	3200	-600	2%	-0.4%	9950	75	8	199	36	2%	0.4%	
18		RDE	16	2000	100	3200	600	2%	0.4%	9950	75	77	199	227	2%	2.3%	
19		RDE	16	2000	0	3200	300	2%	0.2%	9950	75	10	199	19	2%	0.2%	
20	WLTC	16	1000	0	3200	600	2%	0.4%	9950	50	35	199	130	2%	1.3%		
21	Before service 2023	WLTC	16	1000	0	3200	-200	2%	-0.1%	9950	50	5	199	2	2%	0.0%	
22		WLTC	16	1000	0	3200	-100	2%	-0.1%	9950	50	3	199	-3	2%	0.0%	
23		RDE	16	2000	0	3200	100	2%	0.1%	9950	75	3	199	5	2%	0.0%	
24		RDE	16	2000	0	3200	200	2%	0.1%	9950	75	5	199	-16	2%	-0.2%	
25		WLTC	16	1000	0	3200	-200	2%	-0.1%	9950	50	28	199	51	2%	0.5%	
26		WLTC	16	1000	0	3200	0	2%	0.0%	9950	50	4	199	-10	2%	-0.1%	
27		RDE	16	2000	0	3200	-400	2%	-0.2%	9950	75	23	199	41	2%	0.4%	
28		RDE	16	2000	0	3200	-300	2%	-0.2%	9950	75	5	199	15	2%	0.1%	
Average					3.6			-143				14.6			32		0.2%
Standard deviation					18.9			345.8				32.8			161.3		

Figure 3-1 Span drift results for PEMS type 1 ND-IR based CO₂ and CO analyzers from 28 PEMS tests

The collected zero and span drift data indicate that the ND-UV device accounting for NO performed well within the requirements of current regulation. The zero drifts remain typically between ± 0.7 ppm with one exception, which resulted in a 1.9 ppm drift. The average NO zero drift from all results was 0.3 ppm, with a standard deviation of 0.4 ppm. Correspondingly, the average span drift for NO was 1.7 ppm or 0.1 %, with 27 samples of 28 remaining within a ± 0.2

% margin. One of the 28 tests indicated increased drift for both zero and span, albeit the results still remain within the permissible limits. The results were found overall robust and independent regardless of the PEMS condition, i.e. aged or serviced.

Similarly, the NO₂ pre/post response data indicate that the ND-UV remain relatively consistent throughout the campaign, as an average zero drift of 1.3 ppm was noted with most of the tests reaching a drift below ± 2 ppm. However, there were five samples of zero drifts recorded which would not pass the requirements of the latest, Euro 6e regulation. Additionally, one zero drift responded such that it would exceed the RDE4 criteria. The last mentioned was found in the same test where increased NO drift values were seen. After discussing with the manufacturer, the UV source was investigated. The UV light source was concluded to have started to deteriorate; hence the unit was immediately replaced. The reason for excessive zero drift in the cases where Euro 6e limits were exceeded, was chronologically random and remain unknown. The span drift for NO₂ remain relatively stable apart from two cases, with one of the occasions being caused by the defect UV source. The second test with high values was recorded within a longer test campaign, yet no particular trend for increased drift was seen in the next test.

No systematic trends related to NO or NO₂ (or NO_x) drifts were found for neither zero nor span as shown in Figure 3-2.

Table 3-3 NO and NO₂ pre/post response for PEMS type 1 ND-IR between years 2021 to 2023.

Test #	Timeline	Test type	NO ND-UV						NO ₂ ND-UV							
			span standard	Permissible zero drift	zero drift	Permissible span drift	span drift	Permissible span drift	span drift	span standard	Permissible zero drift	zero drift	Permissible span drift	span drift	Permissible span drift	span drift
			[ppm]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[%]	[%]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[ppm]	[%]	[%]
1	Before service 2021	WLTC	3059	5	0.6	61	0.9	2%	0.0%	1500	5	-0.1	30	0.8	2%	0.1%
2		RDE	3059	5	0.3	61	3.1	2%	0.1%	1500	5	1.0	30	-0.2	2%	0.0%
3		WLTC	3059	5	0.2	61	1.1	2%	0.0%	1500	5	-0.2	30	-0.9	2%	-0.1%
4		RDE	3059	5	0.7	61	5.3	2%	0.2%	1500	5	3.3	30	0.8	2%	0.1%
5		RDE	3059	5	0.1	61	3.8	2%	0.1%	1500	5	4.7	30	2.6	2%	0.2%
6		RDE	3059	5	-0.4	61	-4.9	2%	-0.2%	1500	5	0.7	30	-2.0	2%	-0.1%
7	After service 2021	WLTC	3060	5	0.5	61	1.4	2%	0.0%	1500	5	-0.2	30	0.8	2%	0.1%
8		WLTC	3060	5	0.4	61	1.4	2%	0.0%	1500	5	-0.1	30	2.2	2%	0.1%
9		WLTC	3060	5	0.1	61	-0.7	2%	0.0%	1500	5	-0.7	30	0.0	2%	0.0%
10	Before service 2022	WLTC	3060	5	0.5	61	0.4	2%	0.0%	1500	5	2.6	30	1.0	2%	0.1%
11		WLTC	3060	5	0.0	61	0.4	2%	0.0%	1500	5	1.8	30	-0.9	2%	-0.1%
12		WLTC	3060	5	0.5	61	1.1	2%	0.0%	1500	5	3.2	30	-0.3	2%	0.0%
13		RDE	3060	5	0.3	61	1.0	2%	0.0%	1500	5	1.0	30	-0.2	2%	0.0%
14		WLTC	3060	5	0.3	61	4.9	2%	0.2%	1500	5	2.4	30	0.5	2%	0.0%
15		WLTC	3060	5	0.5	61	3.3	2%	0.1%	1500	5	1.9	30	1.1	2%	0.1%
16		RDE	3060	5	0.0	61	2.1	2%	0.1%	1500	5	0.7	30	0.9	2%	0.1%
17		RDE	3060	5	0.2	61	2.4	2%	0.1%	1500	5	4.1	30	2.7	2%	0.2%
18		RDE	3060	5	0.5	61	3.6	2%	0.1%	625	5	0.3	13	0.7	2%	0.1%
19		RDE	3060	5	0.3	61	0.1	2%	0.0%	625	5	-0.9	13	-1.4	2%	-0.2%
20	WLTC	3060	5	1.9	61	12.9	2%	0.4%	625	5	6.7	13	4.6	2%	0.7%	
21	Before service 2023	WLTC	1255	5	0.1	25	0.2	2%	0.0%	625	5	0.2	13	0.1	2%	0.0%
22		WLTC	1255	5	0.2	25	1.3	2%	0.1%	625	5	0.6	13	-0.4	2%	-0.1%
23		RDE	1255	5	0.3	25	1.2	2%	0.1%	625	5	-0.5	13	1.4	2%	0.2%
24		RDE	1255	5	0.1	25	0.0	2%	0.0%	625	5	0.6	13	1.4	2%	0.2%
25		WLTC	1255	5	0.2	25	0.0	2%	0.0%	625	5	-0.6	13	-10.2	2%	-1.6%
26		WLTC	1255	5	0.2	25	0.2	2%	0.0%	625	5	0.0	13	1.3	2%	0.2%
27		RDE	1255	5	0.4	25	0.8	2%	0.1%	625	5	2.3	13	0.3	2%	0.1%
28		RDE	1255	5	0.1	25	0.7	2%	0.1%	625	5	0.6	13	0.9	2%	0.1%
Average					0.3		1.7		0.1%			1.3		0.3		0.01%
Standard deviation					0.4		2.9					1.8		2.4		

Figure 3-2 Span drift results for PEMS type 1 ND-UV based NO and NO₂ analyzers from 28 PEMS tests

Equally, the PN zero drift was monitored throughout the testing. A summary of the PN zero response is shown in Table 3-4. During 2021, severe problems were noted for the ADC based PN PEMS. The PN device typically operated normally, albeit the device suffered from continuous and reoccurring error messages, which prevented to monitor PN zero. This issue was addressed together with the manufacturer, and the device was eventually serviced. However, similar problems continued in a minor scale ca. half a year later, which resulted in the ADC being replaced during the 2022 service. During years 2021 and 2022, the variation of the recorded zero values were relatively high. At highest, the zero drift was ca. 2700 #/cm³.

In 2023, the zero drift response of the ADC remained more stable. Typically, a PN drift below 230 #/cm³ was seen. Further, the initial zero values were remarkable lower that for the previous unit, ca. 700 #/cm³ for a pre- test on average, correspondingly ca. 800 #/cm³ for the post tests.

Since the permissible PN zero is set at 5000 #/cm³, all successfully conducted PN zero tests were within the permissible limits. However, it should also be noted that the 5000 #/cm³ limit may be considered relatively high. Also, the ADC based unit is unable to detect any signal difference between ambient air without a HEPA filter installed compared to samples collected through a HEPA filter.

Table 3-4 Pre and post test response for ADC based PN PEMS from 28 PEMS tests

Test #	Timeline	Test type	PN			
			ADC			
			PN zero pre	PN zero post	PN zero drift	
			[p/cm ³]	[p/cm ³]	[p/cm ³]	%
1	Before service 2021	WLTC	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
2		RDE	1428	n/a	n/a	n/a
3		WLTC	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
4		RDE	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
5		RDE	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
6		RDE	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a
7	After service 2021	WLTC	2543	2336	-207	-8 %
8		WLTC	1701	1669	-32	-2 %
9		WLTC	1693	2509	816	48 %
10	Before service 2022	WLTC	927	n/a	n/a	n/a
11		WLTC	1773	n/a	n/a	n/a
12		WLTC	1182	1564	382	32 %
13		RDE	4375	1618	-2757	-63 %
14		WLTC	1331	1494	163	12 %
15		WLTC	n/a	2025	n/a	n/a
16		RDE	1499	1272	-226	-15 %
17		RDE	n/a	1018	n/a	n/a
18		RDE	1532	4323	2791	182 %
19		RDE	1643	n/a	n/a	n/a
20	WLTC	n/a	1495	n/a	n/a	
21	Before service 2023	WLTC	670	647	-23	-3 %
22		WLTC	781	810	29	4 %
23		RDE	707	617	-90	-13 %
24		RDE	699	927	228	33 %
25		WLTC	762	775	14	2 %
26		WLTC	587	1183	596	101 %
27		RDE	763	842	79	10 %
28		RDE	646	657	11	2 %
Average					111	20 %
Standard deviation			881	919	1050	

The general observations obtained from the pre/post tests for the type 1 PEMS device are:

- The results obtained between 2021 - 2023 suggest that any changes in the condition of the PEMS devices may be identified based on long term pre/post response trends.
- The current limits for the permissible analyser drift limits may be well met even with ageing or deteriorated devices.
- Based on long term tests, permissible pre/post-test threshold for gaseous components could be reduced from 2 % to sub 1 % limit depending on device technology
 - ND-IR drift was typically within ± 0.5 %
 - ND-UV drift was typically within ± 0.2 %
- The ADC based PN analyser suffered from continuous internal errors. Rapid deterioration occurred between the service intervals, which prevented to successfully conduct pre/post testing.
 - When working properly, the typical zero values was below 1000 #/cm³ with a modest analyser drift.

3.2 In laboratory testing, CVS validations with WLTC

Each PEMS configuration was validated in laboratory conditions. The validation process was performed using a light-duty chassis dynamometer equipped with a CVS based emission sampling system. The test results were then compared against the limits defined the most recent regulations, COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) 2018/1832 and 2023/443. The CVS validations were performed for the two vehicles located in Finland, Skoda Octavia diesel and gasoline respectively. An illustrative overview of the test facility is shown in Figure 3-3 The tests were performed between years 2021 and 2023. The status and test order for the different PEMS configurations tested are shown in table Table 3-5.

Figure 3-3 Laboratory testing of two PEMS devices in the CVS environment

Table 3-5 The different test configurations used in the CVS validations in a chronological order

Test information for CVS validations						
Year	Fuel type	Test type	PEMS type and status		PEMS type and status	
2021	Diesel	WLTC	Type 1	Aged	Type 2	
2021	Gasoline	WLTC	Type 1	Aged	Type 2	
2021	Diesel	WLTC	Type 1	Freshly calibrated	Type 2	Used but serviced
2021	Gasoline	WLTC	Type 1	Freshly calibrated	Type 2	Used but serviced
2021	Gasoline	WLTC	Type 1	Freshly calibrated	Type 2	Used but serviced
2022	Diesel	WLTC	Type 1	Aged	Type 2	Used but serviced
2023	Diesel	WLTC	Type 1	Aged	Type 2	goldenPEMS
2023	Gasoline	WLTC	Type 1	Aged	Type 2	goldenPEMS
2023	Gasoline	WLTC	Type 1	Aged	Type 2	goldenPEMS

The emission results obtained in the CVS validations for the two test vehicles are shown in Table 3-6. The response of the individual channels of the tested PEMS devices were then compared to the CVS results. The absolute permissible tolerances for the PEMS devices were calculated from the CVS response according to the RDE 4 and Euro 6e regulations, which are expressed as permissible absolute deviations, correspondingly shown in Table 3-6. The exhaust characteristics between the diesel and gasoline vehicle were found relatively significant. The CO₂ emissions were ca. 25 – 30 g/km lower for the diesel vehicle with an average value of 126 g/km. CO emissions for the diesel vehicle were also lower compared to the gasoline vehicle, with CO emissions between 10 to 35 mg/km for the diesel, and between 83 – 144 mg/km for the gasoline, respectively. The greatest difference in emission characteristics was seen for PN, with diesel vehicle producing figures between 1.0*10⁹ to 3.6*10¹⁰ #/km, meanwhile the gasoline vehicle produced PN emissions close to the legislative limit, between 2.3*10¹¹ to 4.5*10¹¹ #/km. Surprisingly, the NO_x behavior between the two vehicles were very comparable, with both vehicles

producing NO_x emissions of 27 in average, with a variation between 19 to 35 mg/km. The emission characteristics for both vehicles were found robust over the three-year period and no significant change or deterioration in emission performance was noted.

Table 3-6 CVS emission results from the two test vehicles obtained in laboratory conditions

Test information			CVS results					Permissible tolerance compared to CVS, RDE4					Permissible tolerance compared to CVS, Euro 6e				
type	Test type	Year	CO ₂ [g/km]	CO [mg/km]	NO _x [mg/km]	PN [# /km]	Distance [km]	CO ₂ (g/km)	CO (mg/km)	NO _x (mg/km)	PN [10 ¹¹] (#/km)	Distance (m)	CO ₂ (g/km)	CO (mg/km)	NO _x (mg/km)	PN [10 ¹¹] (#/km)	Distance (m)
Diesel	WLTC	2021	124.1	11	19	1.0E+09	23.3	12	150	15	1.0	250	10	100	10	0.8	250
Diesel	WLTC	2021	130.6	7	26	1.7E+09	23.3	13	150	15	1.0	250	10	100	10	0.8	250
Diesel	WLTC	2022	122.4	13	35	3.6E+10	23.0	12	150	15	1.0	250	10	100	10	0.8	250
Diesel	WLTC	2023	127.0	11	28	1.0E+09	23.2	13	150	15	1.0	250	10	100	10	0.8	250
Gasoline	WLTC	2021	165.3	83	27	4.5E+11	23.3	17	150	15	2.2	250	10	100	10	1.9	250
Gasoline	WLTC	2021	166.3	144	31	2.4E+11	23.2	17	150	15	1.2	250	10	100	10	1.0	250
Gasoline	WLTC	2021	159.6	94	22	2.3E+11	23.2	16	150	15	1.2	250	10	100	10	1.0	250
Gasoline	WLTC	2023	160.4	96	25	3.0E+11	23.1	16	150	15	1.5	250	10	100	10	1.3	250
Gasoline	WLTC	2023	159.9	86	25	3.0E+11	23.2	16	150	15	1.5	250	10	100	10	1.3	250

Table 3-7 shows the deviation for the type 1 PEMS device compared to the laboratory reference. Table 3-8 shows the corresponding results for the type 2 PEMS device. The table includes values in respect to absolute deviation, relative deviation compared to the permissible tolerance and the relative deviation to the laboratory reference. Cells indicated in green indicate a passed results for the individual channel, meanwhile cells marked with red exceed the permissible tolerances defined in the RDE4 regulation. Cells marked in yellow indicate that the results pass RDE4 requirements but exceed the permissible tolerances defined in the Euro 6e update.

The laboratory tests shown in Table 3-7 indicate that the performance of the PEMS type 1 was found somewhat two-folded. The performance of the two ND-IR devices were robust apart from one test conducted in 2021, where the CO failed the meet the permissible tolerance. This problem was already identified during the pre/post- tests as described in chapter 3.1.1. *pre- and post- test response*. On another occasion in 2022, the deviation between the ND-IR CO₂ and the CVS results was found just above the Euro 6e limit defined as 10 g/km, with a deviation of 8 %. This was however yet within the RDE4 limits, which was the most recent regulation declared by the EC at the time being. The ND-UV unit performed well throughout the test campaign, with not a single test exceeding the permissible tolerances defined by either regulation. The deviation of NO_x compared to the CVS was typically below 25 % or 8 mg/km, with an average deviation of 4 mg/km or 15 %. Despite the problems faced in pre/post testing with the ADC PN device, the CVS validation, the greatest problems related to PN validity was related to the vehicle with higher PN emissions. For the diesel vehicle, all results obtained with PN PEMS passed the criteria even with the reduced, Euro6e limits. However, this was not the case for the gasoline vehicle, as only one of the five laboratory tests passed Euro 6e criteria. Furthermore, the ADC based PN PEMS suffered from undershooting the PN results more than -50 % for two cases where the ACD was in an aged condition. One test failed to pass the required distance criteria, which was related to a deviation in the calculations between the OBD and dyno distance.

Table 3-7 PEMS type 1 results compared with the laboratory reference

PEMS TYPE 1																		
Test information				PEMS Deviation compared to CVS [abs]					PEMS Deviation relative to permissible tolerance [%]					PEMS deviation compared to CVS result [%]				
	Test type	PEMS status	Year	ND-IR CO ₂ (g/km)	ND-IR CO (mg/km)	ND-UV NO _x (mg/km)	ADC PN (10 ¹¹ #/km)	Distance (m)	ND-IR CO ₂	ND-IR CO	ND-UV NO _x	ADC PN	Distance	CO ₂	CO	NO _x	PN	Distance
Diesel	WLTC	Aged	2021	5	167	4	0.00	200	37 %	111 %	26 %	0.2 %	80 %	4 %	1474 %	21 %	17 %	1 %
Diesel	WLTC	Freshly calibrated	2021	2	4	5	0.01	278	13 %	2 %	30 %	1 %	111 %	1 %	49 %	17 %	68 %	1 %
Diesel	WLTC	Aged	2022	10	10	5	0.33	20	82 %	7 %	32 %	33 %	8 %	8 %	82 %	14 %	-92 %	0 %
Diesel	WLTC	Aged	2023	6	5	8	0.00	155	51 %	4 %	51 %	0.1 %	62 %	5 %	50 %	28 %	-7 %	1 %
Gasoline	WLTC	Aged	2021	6	10	2	2.27	17	35 %	7 %	13 %	102 %	7 %	4 %	-12 %	7 %	-51 %	0 %
Gasoline	WLTC	Freshly calibrated	2021	8	8	2	1.07	5	49 %	6 %	13 %	88 %	2 %	5 %	-6 %	6 %	44 %	0 %
Gasoline	WLTC	Freshly calibrated	2021	7	10	3	0.87	111	44 %	7 %	17 %	75 %	44 %	4 %	-11 %	12 %	38 %	0 %
Gasoline	WLTC	Aged	2023	5	4	5	1.52	26	33 %	3 %	34 %	100 %	10 %	3 %	-4 %	20 %	-50 %	0 %
Gasoline	WLTC	Aged	2023	5	3	4	1.34	30	29 %	2 %	24 %	88 %	12 %	3 %	-4 %	15 %	-44 %	0 %

Passed

Exceed Euro 6E limits

Exceed RDE 4 limits

The results of the laboratory validations for PEMS type 2 shown in Table 3-8 may be divided into two main entities: Results obtained for the commercial PEMS type 2 device (during the period 2021 to 2022) and test conducted with PEMS type 2 based goldenPEMS (year 2023). The main difference between the two scenarios was that commercial PEMS device type 2 represented a PEMS type 2 device which had been extensively used for type approval and R&D testing for several years, meanwhile the goldenPEMS had only a limited number of RDE tests prior to the laboratory validations described in this chapter. The commercial PEMS device suffered especially from issues related to the ND-IR dedicated for monitoring of CO₂, overestimating the CO₂ emissions both in year 2021 and year 2022. The deviation in CO₂ between the years were comparable, with a deviation of 11 % for the diesel vehicle and 16 to 18 % for the gasoline, respectively. This was not the case for the goldenPEMS, which deviation remain within ± 3 % from the laboratory result. The ND-IR for CO was found robust for both devices, with all results remaining with low relative deviations. The NO_x response was found relatively stable for the goldenPEMS device, with a deviation of – 2 % to 1 % for the gasoline vehicle and ca. 11 % for the diesel car. The NO_x performance was somewhat poorer for the commercial device, although yet performing well within the RDE4 limits in all cases, and one test failing compared to Euro 6e limits. The CPC based PN PEMS analyzer performed typically well with both vehicles. Minor difficulties for the commercial type 2 PN PEMS were seen during the gasoline vehicle tests conducted in 2021, with one of the two test failing to pass the required limits. The goldenPEMS device had least deviation from all PEMS devices tested, with a 30 % deviation for the low PN emitting diesel vehicle, and a ± 7 % deviation for the gasoline vehicle.

Table 3-8 PEMS type 2 results compared with the laboratory reference

PEMS TYPE 2																	
Test information				PEMS Deviation compared to CVS [abs]					PEMS Deviation relative to permissible tolerance [%]				PEMS deviation compared to CVS result [%]				
il type	Test type	PEMS status	Year	ND-IR CO ₂ (g/km)	ND-IR CO (mg/km)	CLD + PAS NO _x (mg/km)	CPC PN (10 ¹¹ #/km)	Distance (m)	ND-IR CO ₂	ND-IR CO	CLD + PAS NO _x	CPC PN	CO ₂	CO	NO _x	PN	Distance
Diesel	WLTC Cold	Used but serviced	2021	14	7	7	0.0	273	116 %	5 %	46 %	0 %	11 %	99 %	26 %	-19 %	1 %
Diesel	WLTC Cold	Used but serviced	2022	14	1	12	0.3	232	107 %	1 %	79 %	34 %	11 %	-8 %	-34 %	-96 %	1 %
Diesel	WLTC Cold	goldenPEMS	2023	3	2	3	0.0	154	25 %	1 %	20 %	0 %	2 %	17 %	11 %	-31 %	1 %
Gasoline	WLTC Cold	Used but serviced	2021	27	19	8	2.1	116	163 %	13 %	56 %	95 %	16 %	13 %	-27 %	88 %	0 %
Gasoline	WLTC Cold	Used but serviced	2021	28	13	0	1.9	106	171 %	9 %	3 %	160 %	18 %	14 %	2 %	83 %	0 %
Gasoline	WLTC Cold	goldenPEMS	2023	5	11	0	0.2	21	31 %	8 %	2 %	15 %	-3 %	-12 %	1 %	-6 %	0 %
Gasoline	WLTC Cold	goldenPEMS	2023	4	12	0	0.2	33	25 %	8 %	3 %	14 %	-3 %	-14 %	-2 %	7 %	0 %

Passed

Exceed Euro 6E limits

Exceed RDE 4 limits

The general observations obtained from the PEMS validations in laboratory conditions are:

- When working as intended, the performance of the current commercial PEMS devices are typically well within current RDE4 and Euro 6e limits
 - The results suggest that device ageing typically increase the deviation compared to laboratory results
 - For PEMS devices used in this work, the ageing effects affected the device performance case by case. E.g., not all ND-IR units faces identical problems.
 - Type 1 PEMS ND-IR and ND-UV units were found robust throughout the three year period, meanwhile type 2 ND-IR suffered from issues with a pre-used device. The ND-IR for the goldenPEMS (type 2 based PEMS) was however satisfactory
- PN PEMS response varied greatly depending on the vehicle exhaust emissions.
 - The tested ADC faced challenges with permissible deviation when the test object produce PN emissions close to the emission limit.

3.3 Comparison of two PEMS devices in RDE conditions

Overall RDE testing was done with 2 different PEMS devices (Type 1 and Type 2) on 4 different vehicles as shown in Table 3-9. During each of the 24 tests, both PEMS systems were mounted on the car at the same time, so the measurements were obtained synchronously.

Table 3-9 Overview of RDE tests done with Type 1 and 2 PEMS devices.

Car model	Tests with Type 1 device	Tests with Type 2 device
Skoda Octavia Diesel	11	11
Skoda Octavia Gasoline	7	7
Toyota CHR Hybrid (G)	3	3
Peugeot 308 Diesel	3	3
Grand Total	24	24

The overall results of exhaust flow measurement show good agreement between the two PEMS systems. The difference between diesel and gasoline vehicles is noticeable, as diesel vehicles generally run with a higher intake air flow. There is also a more random day-to-day variation due to variations in temperature and traffic conditions.

Figure 3-4 Total exhaust mass measured with different PEMS devices are in good agreement. Numbers on x-axis are ambient temperatures during each test.

Distance specific CO₂-emission in grams per kilometer is derived from the combination of exhaust mass flow, tailpipe CO₂-concentrations in ppm, and distance measured with GPS. This leads to greater combined uncertainty due to the higher number of devices involved in the calculation. Furthermore, a synchronization between exhaust flow and CO₂-concentration needs to be done in the post-processing software. However, the agreement between Type 1 and Type 2 devices is still very good.

Figure 3-5 Total CO₂ emission per distance travelled is in good agreement between PEMS devices.

When looking at the CO-emission we see a strong day-to-day variation especially on the Peugeot 308 diesel vehicle. This is due to a number of random factors with the DPF regeneration event having the strongest impact.

Figure 3-6 Overall CO-emissions are low but can vary strongly with random day-to-day factors. Agreement between PEMS devices is reasonable.

Average CO-emissions are generally much lower than the legal limit (1000 mg/km). However, the first few seconds of the test can generate very high CO-concentrations which is shown in Figure 3-7. This poses a clear challenge for the PEMS devices, which need to detect momentary CO-concentrations up to 10 000 ppm while the average during driving is only 5-10 ppm.

Figure 3-7 CO-concentrations can fluctuate strongly during the first 100 seconds on both diesel (left) and gasoline (right).

On the NO_x-emissions, day-to-day variations are still present, as with CO. The deviation between measurement devices (Type1: NDUV, Type 2: CLD+PAS) are noticeable with up to 50% difference between them, but with no clear systematic trend as to which device produces the higher value.

Figure 3-8 Device-to-device variation was up to 17 mg/km and day-to-day variation up to 25 mg/km, which is high compared with current emission limits 80 mg/km for diesel and 60 mg/km for gasoline.

Like CO, concentrations of NO_x in the exhaust resulted in spikes at the beginning of the test. Both devices, however, can detect these spikes. Significant deviation between devices occurs at concentrations below 5 ppm, where one device detects slightly negative values, and the other detects slightly positive values.

Figure 3-9 Both devices can detect spikes in NO_x concentration.

Figure 3-10 The deviation between devices on NO₂ measurement is quite strong. Negative values shall be reported as zero in the final RDE report.

On PN-measurements there is good agreement at higher values, which usually belong to gasoline vehicles. On diesel vehicles there is some day-to-day variance, which namely occurs during DPF regenerating events. The averages, however, are often so low that they are difficult to detect accurately. Values below 10⁹ #/km (which is only <0.2% of the legal limit) are uncertain.

Figure 3-11 PN-emissions under 0.2% of the legal limit are difficult to detect accurately.

24 RDE tests were done with dual (parallel) PEMS devices. The general observations from the RDE tests with dual PEMS devices are:

- CO₂ (fuel consumption) is similar for both types of devices
- Day-to-day variations are mostly larger than device-to-device variation
- CO is very low on average but with high spikes
- DPF-regeneration affects CO, PN, and NO_x
- Low NO₂ values are quite uncertain, and probably best detected with PAS
- Pre- and post-tests are quite time consuming in comparison with the actual test duration

3.4 Correlation of PEMS response between WLTC- and RDE-testing

The results acquired from the laboratory (described in chapter 3.2 *In laboratory testing, CVS validations*) tests indicated that the goldenPEMS in a factory calibrated status was more robust compared to the second commercial type 2 PEMS device. Because of this, the correlation between laboratory testing and the RDE measurements were studied explicitly based on the tests conducted with the in-house type 1 PEMS and the goldenPEMS in factory condition. Because the goldenPEMS (which was based on a PEMS type 2) was tested both in Finland and Denmark, the results obtained with goldenPEMS were used as reference and created a link between these two sites for studying the correlation between the three PEMS devices and their response in relation to laboratory (CVS) and RDE tests. The main objective for comparing the deviations between the laboratory- and RDE tests was to study whether the difference between the tested PEMS devices would remain comparable from the laboratory conditions to RDE conditions. Furthermore, the second objective was to study the response of the different PEMS types compared to the laboratory reference with different vehicle and fuel types. This was anticipated to produce additional information about any variables affecting possible deviations between laboratory grade equipment and the given PEMS units. To comply with these objectives, the tests were conducted in three phases following:

- 1st phase - Laboratory tests with a chassis dynamometer and CVS sampling in Finland using WLTC test cycle: A result comparison between CVS, PEMS type 1 and PEMS type 2 (goldenPEMS in factory condition)
- 2nd phase - RDE tests in Finland: Comparing results between PEMS type 1 (1st unit) and PEMS type 2 (goldenPEMS in factory condition)
- 3rd phase - RDE tests in Denmark: Comparing results between PEMS type 1 (2nd unit) and PEMS type 2 (goldenPEMS in factory condition)

The results were then analysed based on any recorded deviations between the test equipment. These may be divided by two fundamental principles:

1. Laboratory tests: comparing the deviation between the laboratory/CVS result with the two PEMS devices
 - a. CVS vs PEMS type 1
 - b. CVS vs PEMS type 2
2. Laboratory and RDE tests: Comparing the deviation between PEMS type 1 and PEMS type 2 installed simultaneously in the test object per site (Finland and Denmark).

Figure 3-12 shows all trip-based CO₂ emissions for the given vehicle configurations which were simultaneously measured using both PEMS type 1 and goldenPEMS (PEMS type 2). The CO₂ results demonstrate that the vehicle behavior, thus CO₂ emissions between WLTC and RDE varied significantly depending on vehicle (or fuel) type. The gasoline vehicle produced significantly higher CO₂ results in WLTC than in RDE (ca. 160 g/km in WLTC vs 110 g/km in RDE), meanwhile the diesel vehicle was more consistent (127 g/km in WLTC vs 123 g/km in RDE). This is a well-known trend, as especially the fuel consumption of gasoline engines are more sensitive to varying driving conditions, for example share of the cold start compared to trip time, ambient temperatures and load profiles (e.g. throttling), than diesel applications. This proves that despite the methods

used in type approval sets certain requirements for any vehicle types, results obtained in laboratory conditions may not directly compared to emission results obtained in RDE.

Figure 3-13 shows the relative deviation of CO₂ for the two PEMS types in both WLTC and RDE testing with respect to CVS results (only for WLTC) and compared to each other. The results indicate that response of the two PEMS types were somewhat inconsistent. For example, the deviations of the two devices compared to the laboratory equipment, CVS, were not directly comparable. Compared to the CVS results, PEMS type 1 overestimated the CO₂ emissions for both test vehicles, by ca. 3 % for the gasoline vehicle and between ca. 4 - 5 % for the diesel vehicle, meanwhile PEMS type 2 device underestimated the results for the gasoline vehicle by 2 – 3 % but overestimated the CO₂ results for the diesel vehicle by ca. 2 % respectively. As a results, the deviation between the two PEMS devices in WLTC was therefore found vehicle/fuel dependent. Equally, the deviation produced between the two PEMS devices in RDE conditions not found to be in line with the response obtained in laboratory conditions. In the RDE tests, the deviation between the two PEMS types varied even more depending on fuel type. For the gasoline vehicle, the deviation between the two PEMS devices were 5 % for the cold start tests and 2 % for the hot start, meanwhile the deviation for the diesel vehicle was less significant, 0 % for tests conducted in Finland and 3 % in Denmark. By analysing the deviation between the two PEMS devices to absolute trip-based test results as expressed in Figure 3-14, no correlation between the deviation obtained in WLTC and RDE could be found.

Figure 3-12 Recorded trip based CO₂ results with CVS, PEMS type 1 and PEMS type 2

Figure 3-13 Relative deviation for CO₂ between the two PEMS types compared to CVS.

Figure 3-14 Deviation in trip-based CO₂ results between the two PEMS device types in WLTC and in RDE conditions.

Figure 3-15 represents recorded CO emissions for each vehicle and device type. Higher CO emissions were noted for both the gasoline and diesel vehicles in WLTC compared to RDE. Figure 3-16 shows a similar comparison of deviations for the PEMS devices obtained for CO emissions. The deviations for the PEMS devices compared to CVS varied case by case, yet no clear trends could be withdrawn. High fluctuations between the relative deviations compared to the CVS result were noted, but in these cases the absolute results were found very small/insignificant, e.g. for the hot start WLTC with the diesel vehicle (CVS resulting in 2.2 mg/km). The recorded deviations varied throughout all tests between the PEMS devices from -25% to 42%, at most. Because the deviations between the two devices related to the trip-based CO

emissions (in RDE) were typically random in results below 50 mg/km, no direct correlation between the PEMS deviation and absolute CO emissions could be made. However, the results indicate that the deviation between the two PEMS devices decreased for tests producing higher CO emissions, as shown in Figure 3-17, but due to the lack of sufficient data, no direct conclusions could be withdrawn.

Figure 3-15 Recorded trip based CO results with CVS, PEMS type 1 and PEMS type 2

Figure 3-16 Relative deviation for CO between the two PEMS types compared to CVS.

Figure 3-17 Deviation in trip-based CO results between the two PEMS device types in WLTC and in RDE conditions.

Figure 3-18 shows the recorded trip based NO_x emissions for given vehicles and measuring equipment. Compared to CO₂ and CO, the NO_x emission were more consistent between the WLTC and RDE tests. Both vehicles produced relatively low NO_x results, below 30 mg/km in all conditions with one exception. In the RDE test conducted in Denmark, a regeneration event took place, increasing the NO_x emissions to above 100 mg/km. Lowest NO_x emissions were found for the RDE test using the gasoline-hybrid vehicle in Denmark, which produced NO_x results between 5 to 9 mg/km depending on PEMS device. Despite the measured values were typically low, the results demonstrate that the current PEMS devices should be able to cover a broad range of emission concentrations.

The recorded relative deviation for NO_x emissions is shown in Figure 3-19. The corresponding absolute deviations are shown in Figure 3-20. Compared to CVS results, PEMS type 1 overestimated the NO_x emissions for all tests conducted in WLTC. The deviations compared to CVS varied between 15 % to 32 %. PEMS type 2 typically overestimated the NO_x emissions in three tests out of four, but in a lesser extent, between 10 % to 16 %. Results suggest that PEMS type 1 tended to record higher NO_x results compared to PEMS type 2 with three exceptions:

1. RDE cold start for the gasoline tests in Finland. The results between the two PEMS devices agreed within 1 mg/km, which was seen insignificant.
2. RDE cold start tests for both vehicle types in Denmark.
 - a. Despite high relative deviation, the gasoline vehicle produced only ca. 5 mg/km of NO_x, meaning that the deviation in terms of absolute value remain low or, ca. 4.4 mg/km
 - b. The diesel vehicle had a regeneration event, increasing the NO_x emissions over the permissible emission limit, which is explained in more detail in chapter 3.1.3.

Overall results of RDE testing

The deviations between the two PEMS devices were more consistent between WLTC and RDE tests with the diesel vehicle recorded in Finland. In these measurements, the results agreed within a relative deviation between 12 – 32 % or 3 – 5 mg/km. This was however not the case for the gasoline vehicle, because the PEMS type 2 produced 9 to 14 % or 3 – 4 mg/km smaller results in WLTC, meanwhile correlated more satisfactory with PEMS type 1 results in RDE conditions. The calculated relative deviations shown in Figure 3-21 also suggest that the difference in the device response remain modest, within 15 % for all test outside extremely low or high results, i.e. where the NO_x results remain within 18 to 34 mg/km. For tests where either very low or very high NO_x emissions were recorded, the relative difference between the two PEMS devices increased. Another observation that was made is that the response between PEMS type 1 devices located in Finland and Denmark related differently compared to the PEMS type 2. The PEMS type 1 device located in Finland produced typically higher results compared to PEMS device 2 and vice versa.

Figure 3-18 Recorded trip based NO_x results with CVS, PEMS type 1 and PEMS type 2

Figure 3-19 Relative deviation for NO_x between the two PEMS types and CVS results.

Figure 3-20 Absolute deviation for NO_x between the two PEMS types and CVS results.

Figure 3-21 Deviation in trip-based NO_x results between the two PEMS device types in WLTC and in RDE conditions.

The trip-based PN emissions recorded by all devices and given vehicles are shown in Figure 3-22. The PN characteristics between vehicle and fuel type varied drastically. The trip-based PN emissions for the gasoline vehicles were in the range of $1 \cdot 10^{11}$ #/km meanwhile one of the diesel vehicles produced significantly lower PN emissions, in below $1 \cdot 10^9$ #/km. The PN results indicate that the vehicle type (and especially exhaust aftertreatment layout) has a significant effect on vehicle PN emission characteristics. The results also demonstrate that current PEMS devices should be able to cover a large range of particulate concentrations during an RDE trip.

The CVS validations indicated that a clear difference in analyser response took place between the two PN PEMS technologies, ADC based PN and CPC based PN units. This was clearly seen in the response compared to the CVS described in chapter 3.1.2 *In laboratory testing, CVS validations*. The deviations for PN emissions seemed to vary significantly depending on test and test vehicle as shown in Figure 3-23. On one hand, the CPC based PEMS type 2 agreed well with the CVS result obtained from the WLTC cold start with the gasoline vehicle (with approx. a 7 % deviation), meanwhile the difference was larger for the PEMS type 1, ADC based unit, ca. - 44 %. However, the effect was opposite for the hot start WLTC test conducted with the gasoline vehicle and for the both WLTC test conducted with the diesel vehicle. In these tests, PEMS type 2 suffered from greater deviation compared to CVS than PEMS type 1. The deviation between the two PEMS types varied between test to test heavily, between – 92 % to 191 %. The PN results correlated somewhat higher for the diesel vehicle. For the diesel vehicle, PEMS type 2 estimated ca. 36 % lower PN emissions on average, meanwhile the type 2 PEMS responded with 49 % higher PN emissions on average for the gasoline. The reason for this effect is caused the difference in absolute PN emissions emitted by the two vehicle types. This effect is seen in Figure 3-24. The trendline for the recorded deviations show that PEMS type 2 underestimates PN emissions below ca. $1 \cdot 10^{11}$ #/km and overestimates the PN emissions above $1 \cdot 10^{11}$ #/km in relation to PEMS type 1. The correlation between the momentary device response is described in more detail in chapter 3.1.5.3 *Comparing momentary PN response between PEMS type 1 and type 2*. Since the

Figure 3-22 Recorded trip based PN results with CVS, PEMS type 1 and PEMS type 2

Figure 3-23 Relative deviation for PN between the two PEMS types compared to CVS.

Figure 3-24 Deviation in trip-based PN results between the two PEMS device types in WLTC and in RDE conditions.

The total trip exhaust masses recorded by the two PEMS devices are shown in Figure 3-25 and the corresponding deviations are shown in Figure 3-26. The results indicate that typically, PEMS type 1 estimates higher exhaust mass values compared to PEMS type 2. For the gasoline vehicle in WLTC and for the cold start RDE, the deviation between the two PEMS devices was 5 %. Surprisingly, the agreement improved for the gasoline vehicle in RDE hot start, which reduced the deviation close to zero. The difference in cumulative EFM results were milder for the diesel vehicle, 2 % in WLTC and virtually zero for the RDE tests conducted in Finland. The reason for this is that especially during low loads, higher exhaust masses are produced by diesel vehicles, which correspondingly means that the pitot based EFM devices records less data in the low end

of the measuring range, which typically contributes with higher uncertainties. This phenomenon is seen e.g., from the deviations between the EFM responses calculated from a 5 s moving average obtained from the momentary data in WLTC, show in Figure 3-26. Greatest deviations between the two PEMS EFMs takes place in tests where the recorded exhaust mass was low. For the diesel vehicle, the exhaust flow range starts from ca. 20 kg/h, meanwhile the gasoline vehicle produces significant fractions of exhaust within the range of 0 – 20 kg/h. Figure 3-28 indicate that the difference in EFM results between PEMS type 2 and PEMS type 1 depended in this case on the quantity of exhaust mass produced during a trip. PEMS type 2 estimated lower exhaust masses than PEMS type 1 in trips with less than 80 kg exhaust mass produced, meanwhile estimating higher values than PEMS type 1 in trips with exhaust masses over 80 kg. The data suggests that the deviations between two devices recorded WLTC are not constant and may not directly be related to a specific RDE conditions. Instead, the uncertainty of EFM devices is highly dependent on vehicle type and its exhaust flow characteristics.

The data acquired in Denmark was however not completely in line with results obtained in Finland. For both the gasoline-hybrid and the diesel vehicle, recorded deviation between the two EFM devices was -5 % or 5 %. The reasons for this deviation were studied further and described in more detail in chapter 3.1.5 *Assessment of different PEMS device technologies in terms of individual channels*.

Figure 3-25 Recorded total exhaust mass for PEMS type 1 and PEMS type 2

Figure 3-26 Relative deviation for exhaust mass between the two PEMS types

Figure 3-27 Deviation between PEMS type 2 and PEMS type 1 EFM reading in relation to the exhaust mass collected from PEMS type 2 data.

Figure 3-28 Deviation in cumulative EFM results between the two PEMS device types in WLTC and in RDE conditions.

Table 3-10 shows an overall result summary of the vehicle tests that were also used as background for correlation analysis described in this chapter.

Table 3-10 Comparison of measurement results from PEMS type 1 and PEMS type 2 (goldenPEMS) on the two vehicles in laboratory (WLTC) and real-world (RDE) conditions for all four vehicles.

Average concentration					
Test type	Component	Unit	PEMS type 1	PEMS type 2	Deviation
WLTC Gasoline Finland	O ₂	[%]	11.4	11.2	2 %
	CO	ppm	54.2	68.0	-20 %
	NO	ppm	20.0	16.8	19 %
	NO ₂	ppm	1.3	0.7	93 %
	PN	#/cm ³	1.4E+05	2.7E+05	-49 %
	EFM	kg/h	41.5	39.6	5 %
Average concentration					
RDE Gasoline Finland	CO ₂	[%]	14.1	14.6	-3 %
	CO	ppm	41.0	67.0	-39 %
	NO	ppm	14.3	12.0	19 %
	NO ₂	ppm	3.2	2.2	47 %
	PN	#/cm ³	1.1E+05	1.6E+05	-30 %
	EFM	kg/h	30.2	28.8	5 %
Average concentration					
WLTC Diesel Finland	CO ₂	[%]	5.9	5.9	1 %
	CO	ppm	-1.3	12.3	-111 %
	NO	ppm	16.2	15.3	7 %
	NO ₂	ppm	2.5	1.0	163 %
	PN	#/cm ³	821	562	46 %
	EFM	kg/h	61.4	59.9	3 %
Average concentration					
RDE Diesel Finland	CO ₂	[%]	6.8	6.7	1 %
	CO	ppm	9.9	14.3	-31 %
	NO	ppm	13.7	12.8	8 %
	NO ₂	ppm	3.8	0.9	306 %
	PN	#/cm ³	697	288	142 %
	EFM	kg/h	62.2	62.3	0 %
Average concentration					
RDE Hybrid Denmark	O ₂	[%]	6.2	9.8	-37 %
	CO	ppm	123	80	54 %
	NO	ppm	3.7	4.6	-18 %
	O ₂	ppm	-3.5	2.1	-267 %
	Pn	#/cm ³	2.80E+05	6.40E+05	-57 %
	EFM	kg/h	30.3	28.7	6 %
Average concentration					
RDE Diesel Denmark	O ₂	[%]	6	5.9	3 %
	CO	ppm	153	134	14 %
	NO	ppm	29.9	31.2	-4 %
	O ₂	ppm	-2.1	1.8	-212 %
	Pn	#/cm ³	1.30E+05	1.00E+05	29 %
	EFM	kg/h	67.7	70.3	-4 %

Average trip results					
Test type	Component	Unit	PEMS type 1	PEMS type 2	Deviation
WLTC Gasoline Finland	CO ₂	g/km	164.5	155.9	6 %
	CO	mg/km	83.0	74.5	11 %
	NO	mg/km	27.0	23.4	15 %
	NO ₂	mg/km	1.3	0.8	68 %
	PN	#/km	1.7E+11	3.2E+11	-48 %
	EFM	kg/km	0.9	0.9	5 %
Average trip results					
RDE Gasoline Finland	CO ₂	g/km	109.9	103.3	6 %
	CO	mg/km	35.0	42.7	-18 %
	NO	mg/km	14.6	16.3	-11 %
	NO ₂	mg/km	3.0	1.9	54 %
	PN	#/km	7.1E+10	1.0E+11	-30 %
	EFM	kg/km	0.5	0.5	5 %
Average trip results					
WLTC Diesel Finland	CO ₂	g/km	133.5	130.1	3 %
	CO	mg/km	15.9	12.4	28 %
	NO	mg/km	30.8	29.6	4 %
	NO ₂	mg/km	4.7	1.3	256 %
	PN	#/km	9.3E+08	6.9E+08	35 %
	EFM	kg/km	1.3	1.3	2 %
Average trip results					
RDE Diesel Finland	CO ₂	g/km	119.9	120.2	0 %
	CO	mg/km	11.3	13.7	-17 %
	NO	mg/km	30.0	29.0	3 %
	NO ₂	mg/km	4.7	1.6	198 %
	PN	#/km	6.1E+08	2.7E+08	122 %
	EFM	kg/km	1.1	1.1	0 %
Average trip results					
RDE Hybrid Denmark	CO ₂	g/km	116.7	110.3	6 %
	CO	mg/km	77	32.3	140 %
	NO	mg/km	8.3	7.1	17 %
	NO ₂	mg/km	-3.3	2.4	-240 %
	Pn	#/km	1.30E+11	3.80E+11	-66 %
	EFM	kg/km	0.6	0.6	5 %
Average trip result					
RDE Diesel Denmark	CO ₂	g/km	135.6	139.2	-3 %
	CO	mg/km	209	188	11 %
	NO	mg/km	109	114	-5 %
	NO ₂	mg/km	-3.7	3.9	-195 %
	Pn	#/km	1.80E+11	1.70E+11	7 %
	EFM	kg/km	1.2	1.3	-5 %

Based on the content described in this chapter, following conclusions may be withdrawn:

- The results suggest that the correlation between laboratory dynamometer and RDE tests were more evident for some emissions components than others. The findings of these trends may be summarized per PEMS channel following:
 - CO₂ - Despite agreement for the two PEMS devices were typically satisfactory, no evident correlation between the deviation obtained in WLTC and RDE was found.

The difference in analyser response were found rather dependent of vehicle/fuel type.

- CO – The deviation for analyser response was found relatively random especially for results with low total CO emissions. This was most likely caused by the variation in exhaust matrix. Because of this the CO analyser is required to cover a wide range of concentrations (e.g. high concentrations produced during cold starts, but remain low when EATS is warm), and yet an extensive calibration range is required. The agreement between the two PEMS devices improved for higher CO emissions and vice versa. However, the deviations between the two PEMS devices in respect to CO emissions obtained in WLTC were found within the data set produced in RDE.
- NO_x - All test vehicles typically produced relatively low NO_x emissions during normal operation. In these cases, the two PEMS types agreed within $\pm 12\%$ both in laboratory and in RDE testing. The difference between the device response was lowest (ca. 3 - 4%) for the gasoline vehicle measured in RDE conditions in Finland. The results showed that ND-UV unit in this cases typically recorded higher NO_x results compared to the PAS device. Challenges in device agreement was seen when extremely low or high NO_x emissions were emitted.
- PN – The agreement between the two PN PEMS devices were found highly dependent on vehicle PN emissions. Highest estimated agreement between the two technology types was approximated when the vehicles would produce around $1 \cdot 10^{11}$ #/km. Meanwhile, the ADC based PN device agreed better with the CVS/laboratory result for tests producing lower PN, the deviation between CVS results and PN PEMS was lower for the CPC based PN device for tests with higher PN emissions. The results suggest that the two PN PEMS devices may be tuned for different concentrations. The data produced both in laboratory and in RDE conditions indicate similar trends and thus a relatively good correlation.
- EFM – The deviations between the two pitot based EFM devices were generally relatively minor. The EFMs agreed better for the diesel vehicle compared to the gasoline counterparts. This is a result of engine characteristics, as the diesel engines lack throttling effects. This in turn results that the lowest exhaust mass produced by the engine typically remain above the last 3 % of the measuring range.

3.5 Assessment of different PEMS device technologies in terms of individual channels

Results from the two PEMS systems match adequately on total CO₂ in terms of mass per km. For diesel vehicles the deviation is below 3% and for gasoline vehicles it is below 6%. This shows that the combined measurement of gas concentration, mass flow, and distance travelled agrees. However, the average gas concentration is quite far off on the hybrid vehicle. This is explained in Figure 3-29 and Figure 3-30.

Figure 3-29 The transient operation of the hybrid drivetrain (left) leads to big differences in detected CO₂ concentrations. The problem does not occur with the diesel car (right). Figure shows running average concentration throughout a 90-minute RDE test.

When the engine turns off, the exhaust mass flow almost instantaneously drops to zero. The difference in measured CO₂ concentration during engine stops therefore does not impact the total mass of CO₂.

Figure 3-30 PEMS Type 2 reacts significantly slower to the on-off operation of the hybrid engine. However, since the exhaust flow is close to zero while engine stops it does not lead to large differences in overall CO₂ mass emission. Figure shows instantaneous concentrations during the later portion of a 90-minute RDE test.

CO measured by the two systems are agreeing well despite the seemingly high relative deviation. The thing to notice is that average concentrations of CO on modern vehicles are extremely low, except for the first couple of minutes after a cold start. The challenge is therefore to measure very high concentrations (>1 %_{vol}) for a short period, which requires high span gas concentrations, even when the average of a 90-minute test comes close to zero. This is shown in Figure 3-31.

Figure 3-31 Running average of CO concentrations are remarkably high at the beginning of the test (cold engine) but almost insignificant by the end of test. The spike on the diesel engine (right) at the end of the test was caused by a DPF regeneration event.

For NO measurement a similar observation as for CO is applicable. As an average, values for the cars are well below legal limits, even close to zero, but immediately after a cold start, there are spikes that challenge the PEMS equipment. The correlation between the PEMS systems is, however, appropriate as seen in Figure 3-32.

Figure 3-32 NO concentration is detected equally well by the two types of PEMS.

When it comes to NO₂ there are substantial differences between the PEMS systems, using different types of sensors. Since the tailpipe concentrations is also very low, detection at this level is problematic as seen in Figure 3-34.

Figure 3-34 NO₂ concentration measurements are extremely low and suffer from significant drift on the Type 1 PEMS (NDUV).

Looking at mass flow from the exhaust, the hybrid car is more problematic than the diesel. In general, mass flow is more precisely measured from diesel cars, because flow is higher, and the gas has less moisture. This is shown in Figure 3-35.

Figure 3-35 Exhaust mass flow from the hybrid gasoline engine is not detected equally - presumably due to high moisture content leading to condensation. Diesel exhaust is drier by nature due to the higher excess-air ratio.

The first portion of the 90-minute RDE test represents city driving where the hybrid engine goes on and off. This leads to greater uncertainties in the exhaust mass flow calculation.

Particle number concentrations on the hybrid vehicle are not detected equally by the PEMS systems. Type 1 PEMS detects spikes better than Type 2 but significantly underestimates average concentration as well as the total emission in #/km on the hybrid vehicle. On the diesel vehicle PEMS Type 2 produces a slightly higher average than Type 1. Tailpipe PN-concentrations on diesel vehicles are low, approaching ambient levels, while gasoline engines PN levels are higher. This is shown in Figure 3-36. Total PN-emission in #/km (Table 3-10) also differs noticeably between the PEMS systems without any clear trend as to which sensor type eventually measures too high or too low.

Figure 3-36 Running average of particle number concentrations on the hybrid vehicle (left) and on the diesel vehicle (right).

To sum up, according to Table 3-10 and Figure 3-29 - Figure 3-36.

- CO₂ is problematic on hybrid vehicles due to different response time of analyzers but on all other vehicles it is detected adequately by both PEMS systems.
- CO can be extremely high at engine startup (>10,000 ppm). The average, however, is well below legal limits for all vehicles tested and there is overall agreement between the two PEMS systems, except for the gasoline hybrid.
- NO is detected reasonably well by both PEMS types.
- NO₂ is typically less than 4 ppm average which is not detected well by Type 1 (NDUV).
- Exhaust mass flow measurement is challenging on hybrid gasoline vehicles due to high flow and high moisture at startup.
- Measured PN can vary by more than ±50% depending on measurement system.

Negative values of CO and NO₂ are sometimes indicated by the PEMS sensors. PEMS Type 1 records these values as negative, PEMS Type 2 records them as zero. PEMS Type 1 can therefore produce a negative end-result, while Type 2 cannot.

The work also resulted in some practical observations from the RDE test crew:

- There is a significant day-to-day variance even on the same vehicle on the same route with the same driver (as described in Section 3.3).
- Limits for VA_pos are set independently of vehicle power and weight. Depending on the type of vehicle they can lead to unsuitable (high and low) accelerations in urban and motorway driving. For instance, a low powered car must be pushed hard, while a higher powered car must be driven prudently.
- Limits for RPA in extra-urban and motorway driving require the car to be driven with frequent speed changes, the normality of which could be questioned. This is sometimes referred to as “pedal-pumping”.
- It is not possible to avoid particulate filter regeneration during tests. However, it is possible to stay within the legal Pn-limit even when regenerating during test.
- Actual “cold start” conditions are hard to replicate. Vehicle may not be entirely cold after 6 hours in a garage.
- 90-minute test is not representative of a typical car trip. In reality, trips are shorter, thus cars will have more cold-starts.

4 Golden PEMS

4.1 Implementation of golden standards

As the objective for implementing a goldenPEMS was to improve the procedures and analysers used for PEMS/RDE testing, all available PEMS channels were studied during the campaign. The goldenPEMS was eventually disassembled and analysed separately by the consortium members working within the MetroPEMS project. The studies conducted explicitly for the different PEMS channels and devices related to goldenPEMS are described in more detail in following documents:

GasPEMS: MetroPEMS deliverable D1 “Validation report on low amount fraction i.e. below 10 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ primary reference gas standards of NO_2 demonstrating an uncertainty of $\leq 1\%$ ” and D2 “Best practice guide on the use of high amount fraction i.e. up to at least 2500 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ NO_2 reference materials”.

PN PEMS: MetroPEMS deliverable D4 “Report on a harmonisation strategy and measurement uncertainty for Particle Number-Portable Emission Measurement Systems (PN-PEMS) calibration in laboratory conditions. This will include characterisation of i) linearity and counting efficiencies ii) particle size dependence (at least up to 10^4 particles/ cm^3 and four sizes), and iii) dynamic flow behaviour including the determination of aerosol sampling and handling effects”.

EFM: MetroPEMS deliverable D7 “Report and recommendations on a generic calibration procedure for transferring (SI-traceable) calibration of PEMS EFM gas flow in (controlled) lab conditions to actual Real Driving Emission (RDE) driving test condition exhaust gas flow measurements, including the effect on PEMS uncertainty”.

Because no physical changes were made for the goldenPEMS device, only limited practical implementations could be directly applied with the device. These limitations meant that only improvements for calibration and post processing procedures were applicable. This chapter describes therefore solely procedures which were directly implemented during the final assessment of the goldenPEMS. Factors, findings, and recommendations directly related to studies, which affect measurement uncertainty are described in the other deliverables announced above.

During the process of exploiting the main issues related to technologies available for the goldenPEMS, potential improvements related to direct calibration procedures of the NO_2 channel were identified. It was found that when adapting calibration standards for NO_2 in a nitrogen matrix, the PAS based NO_2 analyser would produce a non-linear calibration response between 0 – 2000 ppm. As a result, NPL created a sophisticated calibration curve based on multiple NO_2 span concentrations (in nitrogen matrix), which then could be used for correcting any errors caused by the non-linear trend. Additionally, NPL implemented a spectrum of NO_2 standards in a synthetic air (SA) matrix. For the NO_2 standards in SA matrix, the calibration function was found linear. Because the calibration functions for both matrixes were pre-defined in the NPL laboratory, these functions could be directly applied in field (e.g. RDE testing) by using only one gas standard, regardless of gas matrix. The idea was to perform the necessary (non-linear or linear) corrections

during the post processing of recorded data. Similar calibration response was analysed for the other channels, CO₂, CO and NO, but because the bias was not seen as significant.

After the goldenPEMS devices had received its golden calibration, the device was sent to the field for PEMS testing. On site, all calibration curves were immediately checked for stability using available calibration gases. Table 4-1 shows the results obtained from the conducted stability tests for NO₂. The span response for both NO₂ in nitrogen and in air matrixes were identified to have shifted from the values defined at NPL. By applying the correction function defined in laboratory conditions, no improvement could be identified. The results obtained in the stability check suggest that the calibration function was biased due to an unexpected, untraceable reason.

Table 4-1 The initial calibration check conducted in the field

	Standard	Measured		XLGENLINE calc		Meas dev.	XLGENLINE dev.
	<i>ppm</i>	<i>ppm</i>	<i>uncertainty</i>	<i>ppm</i>	<i>uncertainty</i>	<i>[%]</i>	<i>[%]</i>
NO₂ N2	625.0	661.8	0.1	742.0	0.2	5.9 %	18.7 %
NO₂ Air	10.0	11.0	0.0	9.9	0.0	10.1 %	-0.9 %
	500.0	508.8	0.1	457.8	0.4	1.8 %	-8.4 %
	2000.0	2068.6	0.3	1861.2	1.5	3.4 %	-6.9 %

Because of this unexpected issue, available gas standards were individually introduced during pre/post testing to the goldenPEMS device one by one. Because the 2000 ppm NO₂ standard in SA matrix was seen to significantly exceed the measurement scale, it was decided not to be used during the PEMS tests. Therefore, following standards were used:

1. 10 ppm NO₂ in SA (golden standard)
2. 500 ppm NO₂ in SA (golden standard)
3. 625 ppm NO₂ in nitrogen (regular standard complying with RDE regulation, in house)

The gas standards were introduced to the PEMS in "service mode" by manually introducing gas into analyser using the gas divider delivered with the PEMS device. During the calibration process, the inserted gas flow was monitored, which was set by the gas divider at 1.3 NI/min. The trace of each gas standard was monitored during this process, and when considered stabile, next 5 minutes of the calibration was recorded. The last 200 seconds were then extracted from the data set and the average value of this data was treated as final gas response. The typical pre-test function was avoided in order not to adjust the history of the calibration functions set for the PEMS device, which enabled to follow any long-term analyser drift over the complete test campaign. This process was applied for all tests whenever reasonably applicable. Long stabilization times limited the procedure in three tests. There, only most feasible standards, 500 ppm in SA and 625 ppm in nitrogen were applied.

The measurement data was foremost adjusted based on the pre-test zero and span response as allowed in the RDE regulation. No drift correction or additional adjustment was applied. The adjustment was performed for all applied gases using a linear correction function $y=x*a+b$. The final results were then corrected during data post processing using the adjusted analyser response.

4.2 Pre- and post-test response for goldenPEMS NO₂ channel

The drift response of the PAS based NO₂ analyser used in the goldenPEMS was monitored with given gas standards. The device drift was defined based on the recorded average trends obtained from the pre- and post-tests. The recorded drift responses are shown in Table 4-2. Five of the performed pre- and post-test were conducted in laboratory conditions (during WLTC testing), and three tests were conducted in RDE conditions. In the laboratory environment, ambient temperature was between 18.5 °C and 24.2 °C. The ambient temperature during RDE testing was significantly lower, with temperatures ranging from 1.5 °C to 9.6 °C. Throughout all tests, the recorded zero drifts with used standards were mild. However, compared to zero in nitrogen, zero in SA was seen moderately more stable, within ± 0.2 ppm per test, meanwhile corresponding drifts for zero as nitrogen was between -1.4 ppm and 0.5 ppm. For four out of five laboratory tests, the span drifts were found within current RDE limits for all standards used. However, in one of the tests (fourth test in order) in laboratory conditions, the drift response was seen increasing with 625 ppm in nitrogen. The reason for the instability in this particular test remain unknown. The pre/post-test procedure was exactly the same as for the other tests, and thus no device errors or other abnormalities took place.

In RDE tests, the drift response for NO₂ (625 ppm) in the nitrogen matrix exceeded in all three repetitions. This was not the case for the NO₂ standards in SA matrix, which was found more stable in the given conditions. The drift response with 10 ppm NO₂ pass the permissible drift requirements in all cases, meanwhile only one of the tests conducted with 500 ppm failed due to excessive drift. Despite the relative drift for the 10 ppm was between ± 10 % the recorded drifts should still be considered insignificant because the absolute drift values remain within ± 1.1 ppm. Likewise, the calibration in colder ambient conditions (RDE) with 500 ppm NO₂ in SA was seen more stable compared to the 625 ppm in nitrogen.

The drift response results suggest that the excessive drift for the NO₂ 625 ppm standard in nitrogen is somewhat sensitive to colder ambient conditions, or other factors caused by RDE testing. The standards in SA matrix preserved the calibration with higher success, resulting in lower drift variation and higher stability throughout the test campaign. For 10 ppm NO₂/SA matrix, a high relative span drift was monitored, up to 8 %. This however represents an absolute value of 0.8 ppm, which may be considered as insignificant. The span drift response for the 500 ppm NO₂/SA matrix was moderate, typically below ± 2 % or ± 1.3 ppm.

Table 4-2 The recorded drift response for the goldenPEMS with NO₂ in nitrogen and SA matrixes

Test information				Zero drift, ppm		Span drift, ppm			Span drift, %		
				Zero N ₂	Zero as Air	NO ₂ in N ₂	Span in Air		NO ₂ in N ₂	Span in Air	
Average amb. Temperature [°C]	Min amb. temp. [°C]	Max amb. temp. [°C]	Gas component	NO ₂	NO ₂	NO ₂	NO ₂	NO ₂	NO ₂	NO ₂	NO ₂
			Concentration	Zero	Zero	625 ppm	10	500	625	10	500
			Permissible deviation	3	3	12.5	3	10	2 %	2 %	2 %
21.4	N/A	N/A	WLTC Gasoline	-0.1	-0.1	0.9		0.0	0.1 %		0.0 %
21.4	20.0	24.0	WLTC Diesel	0.2	0.0	-11.3	0.1	0.0	-1.8 %	0.6 %	0.0 %
20.7	19.0	23.8	WLTC Diesel	0.0	0.1	3.1	0.1	-1.1	0.5 %	1.0 %	-0.2 %
20.8	19.4	24.0	WLTC Diesel	0.0		24.7	0.2	1.3	4.0 %		0.3 %
20.5	18.5	24.2	WLTC Diesel	-0.2		1.6	0.2	1.3	0.3 %		0.3 %
5.5	1.9	7.1	RDE Diesel	1.4	-0.2	-13.0	0.2	-8.8	-2.1 %	2.4 %	-1.8 %
6.7	3.5	8.0	RDE Diesel	0.2	0.1	37.4	-1.1	-1.2	6.0 %	-10.7 %	-0.2 %
5.6	1.5	9.6	RDE Diesel	0.5	-0.1	-49.5	0.9	18.0	-7.9 %	9.1 %	3.6 %

4.3 Significance of the NO₂ channel in PEMS testing

The influence of different NO₂ standards was further studied by conducting PEMS validations in laboratory (WLTC tests with CVS) and in RDE conditions. Because the objective was to validate the impact of the goldenPEMS NO₂/ NO_x channel(s), this assessment excluded any channels related to other exhaust components (CO₂, CO and PN). The main issue in comparing laboratory results with PEMS response is that the CVS based method measures explicitly total trip NO_x emissions. As a results, performing a comparison between the response of independent NO_x channels (NO and NO₂) between laboratory analysers/CVS and PEMS was not possible. Furthermore, because the CVS methods utilizes a bag sampling method where the mean value over four phases of the total test are recorded, no momentary (second by second) data may be compared between CVS and PEMS. Because of these issues, the impact of the NO₂ calibration for goldenPEMS were compared with CVS result based on data obtained for total trip NO_x instead. However, because two PEMS devices (type 1 PEMS and goldenPEMS) were used in these tests simultaneously, the impact of NO₂ calibration between the two PEMS types were assessed by comparing the impact on device response with respect to both momentary data and total trip data. This enabled to compare the response of NO, NO₂ and NO_x channels between the two PEMS types. The golden NO₂ standards were mainly applied for the diesel vehicle with one exception, the first WLTC cold start test for the gasoline vehicle. In this case, in addition to the regular 625 ppm NO₂ in nitrogen matrix, 500 ppm NO₂ in SA matrix was used. No other golden standards were applicable due to time constrains, because multiple measuring activities in parallel took place.

Table 4-3 depicts the recorded NO_x emissions the laboratory tests. Here, CVS, PEMS type 1 and goldenPEMS were simultaneously used. The values presented in columns marked with grey represents trip based NO_x emissions recorded by the CVS system. The corresponding permissible NO_x tolerances (defined in the RDE regulation) calculated from the absolute NO_x results are presented next to the absolute trip results. Because both vehicles produce below 30 mg/km of NO_x emissions over the total trip, the permissible tolerance was determined according to the regulatory standards as 12.5 mg/km for Euro 6e and 15 mg/km for RDE4. The measured absolute and relative deviations generated by PEMS type 1 and goldenPEMS (with each individually applied NO₂ standard) are indicated in the columns coloured with green and orange. Cells potentially marked with red represents results which fail the RDE4 limit. Any results potentially marked with yellow represents values exceeding the permissible tolerance of Euro 6e regulation but pass the limits set by RDE4 regulation.

Based on results shown in Table 4-3, all PEMS results clearly pass the permissible tolerances defined by the two RDE regulations. The deviations between CVS and PEMS were in these tests always higher for PEMS type 1 than for the goldenPEMS with any applied standards. In respect to total trip NO_x emissions, the impact of adapting different NO₂ standards with goldenPEMS were generally found relatively minor. Greatest difference was found for the diesel vehicle between the 500 ppm NO₂ calibration in SA matrix and the 625 ppm based NO₂ in nitrogen matrix. By implementing the 500 ppm in SA standard, NO_x emissions increased compared to the 625 ppm NO₂/N₂ calibration ca. 0.5 mg/km at most. The 625 ppm based NO₂/N₂ calibration produced lowest NO_x results, and lowest deviations compared to CVS from the group. The calibration with 10 ppm NO₂/SA matrix recorded NO_x results in between for all cases. Typically, applying the golden standards for the diesel case would slightly increase the trip based NO_x results and corresponding deviations between CVS and goldenPEMS with 0.2 – 0.5 mg/km or ca. 1 – 2 % depending on case. At most, an increase of ca. 0.5 mg/km was seen between the in house 625 ppm standard and the higher golden standard, 500 ppm. For the gasoline vehicle, the effect was opposite. Applying the 500 ppm NO₂/SA calibration, NO₂/NO_x emissions decreased NO_x emissions by 0.1 mg/km. Unfortunately, because only one test was conducted, no quantitative conclusions for the tests conducted with gasoline vehicle could be withdrawn.

Table 4-3 NO_x results obtained in laboratory tests with PEMS type 1 compared to the goldenPEMS with different gas standards.

Test parameters		Permissible tolerance compared to CVS [abs]			NO _x deviation compared to permissible tolerance, abs [mg/km]				NO _x deviation compared to CVS, relative [%]			
					NO span 1255ppm in N ₂				NO span 1255ppm in N ₂			
					NO ₂ span 625 ppm in N ₂	NO ₂ span 625 ppm in N ₂	NO ₂ span 10 ppm in SA	NO ₂ span 500 ppm in SA	NO ₂ span 625 ppm in N ₂	NO ₂ span 625 ppm in N ₂	NO ₂ span 10 ppm in SA	NO ₂ span 500 ppm in SA
WLTC test type	Vehicle type	CVS NO _x result (mg/km)	Permissible NO _x tolerance, RDE4 (mg/km)	Permissible NO _x tolerance, Euro 6e (mg/km)	Type 1 (ND-UV)	goldenPEMS (CLD + PAS)	goldenPEMS (CLD + PAS)	goldenPEMS (CLD + PAS)	Type 1 (ND-UV)	goldenPEMS (CLD + PAS)	goldenPEMS (CLD + PAS)	goldenPEMS (CLD + PAS)
Hot	Diesel	25.3	15	12.5	7.2	3.0	3.0	3.2	28.3 %	11.7 %	11.7 %	12.6 %
Cold	Diesel	27.8	15	12.5	7.7	3.1	3.4	3.5	27.7 %	11.0 %	12.2 %	12.7 %
Hot	Diesel	21.0	15	12.5	6.7	3.4	3.8	3.9	32.0 %	16.2 %	18.0 %	18.6 %
Cold	Gasoline	25.3	15	12.5	5.2	0.3		0.2	20.3 %	1.0 %		0.6 %
Cold	Gasoline	24.7	15	12.5	3.6	0.5			14.6 %	-1.9 %		
Hot	Gasoline	31.0	15	12.5	6.3	4.1			20.4 %	13.3 %		

To illustrate the significance of NO₂ for total NO_x emissions, the ratio between the total recorded NO₂ and NO_x were derived. These results are shown in Table 4-4. As concluded from the laboratory comparison presented in Table 4-3, the ND-UV based PEMS type 1 responded with higher shares of NO₂ compared to goldenPEMS in all WLTC tests. Lowest NO₂ results was recorded for the diesel vehicle with goldenPEMS using the NO₂ standard in a nitrogen matrix. In these tests, implementation of the golden NO₂ standards (in SA matrix) for diesel vehicle typically increased the NO₂ emissions. For the gasoline vehicle, the effect was opposite. However, because the NO₂ standard in SA matrix (500 ppm) was successfully implemented only in one test with the gasoline vehicle, it is challenging to extract any quantitative or conclusive results based on single test results. It should however be noted that the response between the two PEMS technology types, in this case ND-UV and PAS, had generally a greater impact on NO₂ result compared to the influence on channel response between the three NO₂ standards used with the goldenPEMS.

Table 4-4 Share of NO₂ recorded by ND-UV based PEMS type 1 and the goldenPEMS (with three different span standards)

Test parameters		Share of NO ₂ in NO _x emissions			
		NO ₂ span 625 ppm in N ₂	NO ₂ span 625 ppm in N ₂	NO ₂ span 10 ppm in SA	NO ₂ span 500 ppm in SA
WLTC test type	Vehicle type	Commercial PEMS (ND-UV)	goldenPEMS (CLD + PAS)	goldenPEMS (CLD + PAS)	goldenPEMS (CLD + PAS)
Hot	Diesel	14 %	9 %	9 %	10 %
Cold	Diesel	13 %	4 %	5 %	6 %
Hot	Diesel	12 %	5 %	7 %	7 %
Cold	Gasoline	6 %	3 %		2 %
Cold	Gasoline	5 %	3 %		
Hot	Gasoline	3 %	3 %		

Because the test matrix for comparing the NO₂ standards was more comprehensive for the diesel vehicle than for the gasoline, a more detailed analysis and comparison for the NO₂/NO_x results between WLTC and RDE for this vehicle was made. Figure 4-1 presents the NO₂ results for the diesel obtained with goldenPEMS and all applied standards together with results obtained with PEMS type 1 (625 ppm in nitrogen matrix). The corresponding total trip NO_x emission results are shown in Figure 4-3. Like concluded during the laboratory validations, the results indicate that even in RDE conditions, the difference in NO₂ results for the different standards, 10 ppm, 500 ppm in SA matrix and 625 ppm in nitrogen matrix remain in terms of absolute results rather minor. Compared to the WLTC tests, the difference in NO₂ responses obtained with the given NO₂ standards for goldenPEMS roughly doubled in RDE conditions. Because the NO₂ emissions were evidently low to begin with, the highest recorded deviation between the applied standards/calibrations was yet only ca. 1.2 mg/km. Likewise concluded for the WLTC tests, PEMS type 1 recorded higher NO₂ emissions in RDE conditions than the goldenPEMS. Typically, PEMS type 1 estimated up to 11 times higher NO₂ results compared to the goldenPEMS. Because the variation in NO₂ response from test to test between the two devices was found relatively random, no clear correlation between the results obtained with goldenPEMS and PEMS type 1 was found, as shown in Figure 4-2. For example, when goldenPEMS recorded lower NO₂ emissions for WLTC hot start test than for the cold start WLTC, the response for PEMS type 1 was opposite. Similarly, the response in NO₂ emissions between cold and hot start RDE were not found for the two devices comparable. However, it should also be noted that the recorded deviation between

the two device types were significantly greater than the absolute effect of the different standards applied for the goldenPEMS.

Figure 4-1 NO₂ results obtained from goldenPEMS with applied standards together with corresponding NO₂ response for PEMS type 1 for the diesel vehicle in WLTC and RDE

Figure 4-2 Correlation for NO₂ results between goldenPEMS with all applied standards and PEMS type 1 with the 625 ppm in nitrogen matrix.

Figure 4-3 shows the trip NO_x emissions for the same tests as presented for NO₂. Overall, the effect of NO₂ standard and calibration had only a minor effect on the total NO_x outcome. Yet again, PEMS type 1 responded with higher results, mostly affected by the difference produced by NO₂.

Figure 4-3 NO_x results obtained from goldenPEMS with applied standards together with corresponding NO_x response for PEMS type 1 for the diesel vehicle in WLTC and RDE

The difference in NO₂ response between the two test devices and the predominant calibrations are explainable by analysing the momentary NO₂ data. An example of second-by-second data acquired for an RDE test of NO₂ concentrations for both goldenPEMS and for PEMS type 1 are illustrated in Figure 4-4. Two main differences between the PAS based goldenPEMS and PEMS type 1 was found.

1. Deviation in signal trace during a test: The signal trace for NO₂ concentration with PEMS type 1 (ND-UV) starts to slowly increase initiating from around 1000 s after the start, rising close to 5 ppm. The signal eventually settles around ca. 2500 s into the test, remaining at ca. 5 ppm throughout rest of the measurement. This contributes to a steady and continuous increase of the calculated cumulative exhaust mass after the signal shift, as shown in Figure 4-5. One option for addressing this phenomenon is performing a data/drift correction based on pre/post analyser drift data. However, because the signal rise takes place in the middle of the test, and as the trend is evidently non-linear, a linear correction based on pre/post response values would hypothetically overcorrect for the first part of the test and vice versa. Another issue is that the shifted signal trace in the momentary data did not fully correlate with the recorded drift values acquired from the post test. According to the post test response of this particular test, the recorded span drift was 0.33 ppm and zero drift was 2.3ppm. The analyser drift recorded over the pre/post- tests may therefore only partly explain the signal behaviour but did not totally correspond to the magnitude of the presumed signal shift recorded during the test. A similar signal shift seen for PEMS type 1 did not take place with the PAS based goldenPEMS. The recorded trace for the PAS device trend remains stable and to absolute zero bot in the beginning and by the end of the measurement.

2. Unequal signal response time: A significant difference in signal response time between the two device types was found. The signal response time with the PAS based goldenPEMS was far more sensitive compared to the ND-UV based PEMS type 1. This may especially be seen during the largest, rapid spikes with high concentrations occurring during the cold start phase, within 250 s of the test as shown in the example Figure 4-6. In such conditions, the signal response for the PAS was rapid, meanwhile the ND-UV responds with a less steep signal. As a result, the signal response recorded by the ND-UV in such cases presents values less than 50 % of the PAS reading. Equal effects were seen also in conditions where less drastic NO_2 concentrations were recorded, shown in the second example in Figure 4-7.

Figure 4-4 An example of momentary NO_2 response for the goldenPEMS with applied standards compared to the NO_2 response for the ND-UV based PEMS type 1 device in a RDE test.

Figure 4-5 Cumulative NO₂ emissions for an RDE test displayed for the different standards used with goldenPEMS and with PEMS type 1

The impact of the applied golden NO₂ standards were monitored from the momentary data. Figure 4-6 and Figure 4-7 show that the corrected for goldenPEMS using the different standards/calibrations show only a minor shift, below 1ppm, in the signal trace. Apart from the signal shift, no significant effect for the NO₂ trace was found. The results suggest that the golden standards have a greater impact on the pre/post test quality compared to the significance of final trip result itself.

Figure 4-6 A detailed example (initial 250 s) of momentary NO_2 response for the goldenPEMS with applied standards compared to the NO_2 response for the ND-UV based PEMS type 1 device in a RDE test.

Figure 4-7 A detailed example (2000 s – 2500 s) of momentary NO_2 response for the goldenPEMS with applied standards compared to the NO_2 response for the ND-UV based PEMS type 1 device in a RDE test.

5 Summary and conclusion

The work presented in this document describes the main findings from validation and from real world testing performed for four PEMS systems. The objective of the work presented in this report was to study any factors affecting the overall performance of PEMS devices. The different factors were studied by conducting experimental testing using real world applications, both in laboratory conditions and in on road conditions. The methods used in this work was based on applied testing that mainly follows the type-approval regulation currently in force. The main approach of the testing was to initially validate the performance of the PEMS devices in a laboratory using a CVS system and a light-duty chassis dynamometer, followed by a set of RDE testing in two countries, Finland and Denmark. Any deviation or findings extracted from the laboratory validations were compared to the RDE results. The analysis covered topics related to the PEMS system as an entity, but were also analysed in respect to the individual PEMS channels, i.e. CO₂, CO, NO, NO₂, PN, exhaust mass flow analysers.

These themes addressed in this report may be summarized following:

i. General observations

- Pre- and post-tests are already now quite time consuming in comparison with the actual test duration, so efforts to simplify these procedures will allow more time for testing.
- Based on the findings obtained from long-term tests conducted in this work, the permissible analyser drifts over the RDE tests determined in the RDE regulation could be further decreased.
- Device malfunctions or device deterioration may be identified in advance based on pre/post calibration response.
- For NO_x emissions, the contribution of NO is typically in the range of 85 – 95 % of total NO_x. Therefore, special focus on improving NO channels instead of NO₂ are advised.
 - NO is detected reasonably well by the PEMS.
 - NO₂ is typically less than 4 ppm average which is not detected well by a NDUV sensor. Low NO₂ values are quite uncertain, and probably best detected with a PAS.
- EFM lack accuracy in the very low end of their measurement range, typically below 3 – 5 % of the measuring range. The measurement of exhaust mass flow was therefore concluded to be more accurate for diesel vehicles.
 - Exhaust mass flow measurement is challenging on gasoline vehicles due to high flow and high moisture at startup.

ii. Analyser drift during PEMS testing

One of the commercial PEMS devices was repeatedly tested for a three-year period between 2021 – 2023. The device consisted of two ND-IR analysers, dedicated for CO₂ and CO emissions, two ND-UV analysers for NO and NO₂ emissions and an ADC for measuring PN emissions. During this period, the performance characteristics this

particular PEMS device was found well within and below the criteria defined in the RDE regulation. The ND-IR analysers drifted typically below ± 0.5 % over the PEMS measurements. The only exceptions when the analyser drift above its typical ± 0.5 % was for situations where the analyser had clear issues. Correspondingly, the drift of the ND-UV analysers was generally within ± 0.2 %. Greatest problems were found for the ADC unit, which faces multiple problems for the pre-charger and temperature control. These problems caused numerous errors, which resulted in failed tests. The abnormal drift recorded both for the ND-IR and ND-UV units indicated clearly if any device related issues took place. Any potential issues/degradations related to all PEMS channels identified in advance if the trends for analyser drifts are recorded. Based on the results obtained from the long term tests, the permissible analyser drifts could be further reduced.

iii. Factors affecting PEMS performance

The pre- and post-tests typically provided with useful information for evaluating and defining the condition of the PEMS device. When the analysers performed well and as intended in pre- and post tests, the PEMS devices responded also well in the laboratory validations. Any issues related to PEMS hardware was identified both from the pre/post testing and laboratory validations. Factors affecting PEMS performance may be summarized following:

- There is a significant day-to-day variance even on the same vehicle on the same route with the same driver. Day-to-day variations are mostly larger than device-to-device variation.
- Measurement of CO₂ is problematic on hybrid vehicles due to on/off operation of the engine but on all other vehicles it is detected adequately.
- CO concentration can be extremely high at engine startup (>10,000 ppm). The average, however, is well below legal limits for all modern vehicles. Like CO₂, the measurement of CO is more challenging on hybrids.
- DPF-regeneration affects CO, PN, and NO_x emissions. It is not possible to avoid regeneration during tests. However, it is possible to stay within the legal PN-limit even when regenerating during test.
- Measured PN can vary by more than $\pm 50\%$ depending on measurement system. However, the difference between vehicles is much larger, up to several orders of magnitude.
- Negative values of CO and NO₂ are sometimes indicated by the PEMS sensors. Some systems record these values as negative, other systems record them as zero. Consistency should apply.

iv. Correlation between laboratory validations and RDE testing

The performance of the tested PEMS devices varied somewhat between laboratory and RDE testing. The deviations between the two tested PEMS devices were found dependent both on emission type and emission characteristics but also vehicle type. For example, despite the CO₂ results agreed relatively well between the two PEMS types both in laboratory and in RDE, the no clear correlation for the deviations between laboratory tests and RDE could be withdrawn. Because NO_x emissions recorded from most of the vehicles

were low, no systematic trends or correlations between variability for the PEMS devices were found. The performance of the tested PN PEMS analysers varied depending on vehicle type. The results recorded with ADC PN analyser correlated better with the laboratory result for tests producing lower PN emissions, meanwhile the CPC based PN device performed better for tests which resulted in higher PN emissions. The results suggest that the two PN PEMS devices may have been tuned for different emission matrixes. The data produced both in laboratory and in RDE conditions indicated that similar trends and correlation for the recorded deviation occurred.

v. Assessment of potential topics for improving PEMS performance and RDE procedures beyond current state-of-the-art

The work conducted for the goldenPEMS indicated that improving the PEMS methodologies or procedures without modifying the device hardware is challenging. Unfortunately, the calibrations of the gas channels of goldenPEMS were not found robust enough for enabling implementation of novel calibration procedures. However, by optimizing the gas standards, especially related to the gas matrixes, the performance of PEMS devices especially for pre/post-test calibration may potentially be improved. Furthermore, key findings extracted from the work described in this report regarding challenges in RDE testing may be summarized following:

- 90-minute test is not necessary most representative of a typical car trip. In reality, trips are shorter, thus cars will have more cold-starts.
- The limits for VA_pos could be reconsidered. Depending on the type of vehicle they can lead to unsuitable (high and low) accelerations in urban and motorway driving.
- The limits for RPA in extra-urban and motorway driving could be reconsidered as they require the car to be driven with frequent speed changes, the normality of which could be questioned. This is sometimes referred to as “pedal-pumping”.
- Actual “cold start” conditions are hard to replicate. Vehicle may not be entirely cold after 6 hours in a garage.

6 Nomenclature

Acronyms	Description
ADC	Advanced Diffusion Charger
CLD	Chemi Luminesense Detection
CO	Carbon monoxide
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CPC	Condensation particle counter
CVS	Constant volume sampling
DPF	Diesel particulate filter
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ND-UV	Non-Dispersive Ultra Violet Spectroscopy
NO _x	Nitrogen oxides
PAS	Photoacoustic Spectroscopy
PEMS	Portable emissions measurement system
PN	Particle number
PPM	Parts per million
RDE	Real drive emissions
SA	Synthetic air
WLTC	Worldwide harmonized Light-duty vehicles Test Cycle
WLTP	Worldwide Harmonised Light Vehicles Test Procedure

7 References

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